

Life in the shallows

exploring plankton production in the water column.

A teaching guide

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Simulation models QUICK START

If not yet installed, install Powersim 10 Studio Cockpit

- The *Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit* application works only on PCs operating *Microsoft Windows*.
- Visit the *Powersim Studio* download site at <https://powersim.com/download-cockpit/>
- Download *Cockpit* (64-bit or 32-bit; most PCs will be 64-bit).
- Follow instructions provided by *Powersim* to install the software. (Accept default suggestions).

Loading and running a simulation project

- The simulation files all have a common name format: **1D_Exp{x}.sip** where {x} is the experiment number 1..7.
- These files are located together with this document, and share the same doi. Please visit the Zenodo site, as noted in 'Citing this document' to locate and then download the files.
- Once downloaded, and assuming that Powersim Cockpit is installed, the file name should have the *Powersim Studio 10* logo associated with it - clicking on the file name will open the file within the *Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit* application.
- If the logo is not visible, right-click on the file name, and select 'open with' to use Powersim Cockpit as the application.
- The selected simulation model will open into a Home page; just follow the on-screen instructions referencing the detailed instructions in the appropriate Experiment description.

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Preface

This document is one of a series intended to assist in the teaching of ocean literacy and allied aspects of environmental education applied to freshwaters, such as lakes and reservoirs. This particular document targets plankton life and production in the sunlit upper waters.

Much use is made of simulation models. These enable students to experiment with simple representations of the real world.

The model operates within a **Microsoft Windows** application, called **Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit**, which is available for free.

To download this free application, visit this website:

<https://powersim.com/download-cockpit/>

WARNING: Only install Cockpit on a PC that does not contain another Powersim Studio product. Installing Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit if you already have Powersim Studio installed will overwrite Studio!

Acknowledgement to Funders

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Views and opinions expressed are those of the author only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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The simulation models associated with this document was developed using the software **Powersim Studio 10** (www.Powersim.com). The models presented are free for use under the Powersim Studio 10 Cockpit platform.

Glossary

Abiotic – physics and chemistry components of a system.

Allelopath – a chemical produced by one species that may be deleterious to another species and/or signalling to others of the same species.

Ammonium – an important form of dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN) in water bodies. Typically used to refer to both ammonia (NH_3) and ammonium (NH_4^+); the latter form is more abundant at the pH of seawater.

Biomass – the collective mass of organisms, usually given in terms of carbon or nitrogen, as C-biomass or N-biomass.

Biotic – biological components of a system.

Chlorophyll – the most important pigment associated with photosynthesis. Often used as a measure of biomass, for which it is ill suited as the Chl:C ratio is variable by ca. 5 fold.

Competitive advantage – advantage that one species has over another in competition for a common limiting resource, or against a common loss factor (such as a grazer).

Consumer – an organism that consumes biomass and/or dissolved organic nutrients. Consumer activity results in the net decrease in the abundance of organic material in an ecosystem.

Dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN) – ammonium+nitrate+nitrite.

Dynamic – changing with time.

Ecosystem disruptive algal bloom (EDAB) – a form of microalgal growth that, because it is poorly grazed, acts to block the normal functioning of a food web.

Ergocline – energy gradient, specifically a steep energy in a water column, such as that associated with a thermocline.

Eutrophication – an ecosystem status that is sufficient nutrient rich that its behaviour displays damaging characteristics, such as excessive biomass accumulations which may lead to deoxygenation.

Food chain/web – a linked series of inter-relating organisms through which energy and resources (e.g., C, N, P) pass from producer to a series of consumers, with the latter regenerating the inorganic nutrients used by the former. A chain refers to a simple linkage, while a web (which is the common format in nature) refers to complex interconnectivities.

Halocline – an ergocline based on a salt gradient.

Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) – a form of microalgal growth that produces toxins. Those toxins may not affect organisms within the food web, but may accumulate in a animal harvested (and thence becoming toxic to) humans.

Match-mismatch – the alignment of prey and predator growths; a well matched system does not display sharp mal-alignments of these growth, the optimal matched system operating in steady-state. A mismatched system shows sharp separations, and potentially can result in an ecosystem collapse associated with the formation of an EDAB.

Microalgae – any microscopic, unicellular, organism that performs photosynthesis (able to perform phototrophy). These include cyanobacteria and protists. Not all microalgae are planktonic. Almost certainly all microalgae can consume organic nutrients (thus they are able to perform osmotrophy); some can grow in total darkness using such nutrients.

Mixed layer – a zone in the water column which is, relative to adjoining zones, well mixed. Typically refers to the upper 10s -100s m of the water column, stirred by atmospheric processes.

Mixed layer depth (MLD) – the depth of the mixed layer, between the water-air interface and the ergocline (typically, thermocline).

Mixoplankton – a type a protist microalgae that both photosynthesise and eat. Many so-called phytoplankton are actually mixoplankton, consuming prey through a process generally termed as phagotrophy.

Model – a simplification of reality.

Nitrate – the most abundant form of dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN) in water bodies; NO_3^- .

Ocean acidification – the acidification of seawater as a consequence of the dissolution of increasing levels of atmospheric CO_2 into the ocean.

Photon – a package of light energy. Photons collide with a surface of a given area at a given rate, described as a photon flux density (PFD). Full sunlight has a PFD of visible light, as used to support photosynthesis, of ca. $2000 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$.

Photosynthesis – the use of light energy to synthesize organic matter from CO_2 and H_2O . Gross photosynthesis is just that production, while net photosynthesis subtracts any allied costs in respiration and especially nitrate reduction required to support organism growth.

Phytoplankton – a type of microalgae (cyanobacteria or protist) that cannot eat. Many so-called phytoplankton are actually mixoplankton.

Plankton – organisms that are unable to move against currents. This does not preclude them from being motile, and some can migrate vertically many 10s or even 100s m in the water column.

Primary production – production of new organic material in an ecosystem. Usually associated in aquatic ecosystem with phototrophy due to phytoplankton and mixoplankton. Not all primary production enters biomass, however; a significant proportion may be leaked as dissolved organic chemicals into the water and thence support the growth of (heterotrophy in) microbes.

Producer – an organism whose activity results in the net increase in the abundance of organic material in an ecosystem, by fixing CO_2 .

Production – making (typically) biomass.

Protist – a general term for an extremely diverse range of eukaryote microbes. Most protists live as plankton, but many others live with particles, and some are important parasites in other organisms (including humans). The diversity of protists exceeds that of all other eukaryotic organisms combined.

Pycnocline – an ergocline based on a density gradient (which usually results from a combination of temperature and/or salinity gradients).

Relaxed evolution – the loss of efficiency or ultimately of functionality of trait expression due to possession of that trait being of relatively minor consequence for the competitive advantage of the organism.

Self shading – the loss of light supporting photosynthesis resulting from other light absorbing materials (typically, photo-pigment containing organisms) being closer to the light source and thus absorbing, removing, photons.

Simulation model – a mathematical, computational, model which has changes over time as a critical feature.

Spring bloom – the early seasonal (spring) growth of phototrophic organisms (phytoplankton and/or mixoplankton). The term ‘bloom’ is a subjective one, but may be considered to reflect an increase in biomass abundance of ca. 10 fold over the background level.

Steady-state – a condition in which variables are constant. In biological systems, a steady-state system is one in which biomass and nutrient levels are constant over time. In nature, such conditions very rarely exist for any significant period of time.

Thermocline – an ergocline based on a temperature gradient.

Tipping point – a point of sensitivity beyond which return to a previous state requires a significant input of energy and/or resources. In ecology, it typically refers to a fundamental change in food web structure such that different types of organisms come to dominate, perhaps to the total exclusion of formally dominant organisms.

Trophic interactions – interactions between organisms in which energy and/or materials are transferred.

Vertical Eddy Diffusion (VED) – a process through which water and materials therein are mixed vertically by diffusion.

Washout – the loss of material in a system. In plankton ecology, this refers to a situation where the loss of material (for example by eddy diffusion across the ergocline) exceeds the increase (growth) of material in the mixed layer.

Water column – a vertical transect in a body of water, from the surface to an interface (typically either an ergocline or the bottom).

Zooplankton – a type of plankton that feeds on other (prey) organisms, typically by ingesting either the whole prey, or significant components of it. Zooplankton may be characterised in different ways; protist vs metazoan zooplankton, meroplankton vs holoplankton. Protist zooplankton are typically fast-growing efficient unicellular microbes. Metazoan zooplankton are multicellular animals that range from microscopic to many m in length, and typically have complex life cycles. Meroplankton are larval stages of non-planktonic animals (such as barnacles, crabs, starfish); holoplankton are animals that are solely (or effectively so) planktonic throughout their life.

A note to teachers about age suitability and science language

The information provided in this document is intended to support your teaching activities. You are best placed to decide how to make this information suitable, age-appropriate, for your students. Based on the experience of the author, the core concepts may be taught successfully to students from 13 years up. The complexity of the subject can also be developed through to university level.

This document runs through 7 sub-projects, building up from simple concepts to an open-ended, ultimately complex and intellectually engaging simulation. The subject in total can be challenging unless the student understands sufficiently at each step. It is important to work through the sub-projects in turn.

The correct use of science language is important; at each step special terms are explained. There is also a Glossary.

Fit to curriculum

The subject matter of this document may be aligned with various aspects of general teaching curricula. Some indications of this fit are considered here.

Topic	Language	Mathematics	Biology	Chemistry	Physics
a) Interpretation of written evidence	●		●	●	●
b) Written expression	●		●	●	●
c) Structured reporting	●		●	●	●
d) Interpretation of visual evidence and graphs	●	●	●	●	●
e) Calculations, equations, computer coding		●	●	●	●

- Scientific writing has a particular style, often written in the 3rd person ('this was done' etc.); use of the 1st person ('I did ..') is generally not encouraged. Be aware that scientists make errors, and while they should not be biased, bias in their reporting (often as an emergent consequence of brevity, rather than being deliberate) is not uncommon. Science is regularly updated; this means that it is important to balance interpretations of dated literature (which may be more likely to identify 'established knowledge') against views expressed in recent literature (which may identify problems with established 'facts'). Typically a text science book is already dated, and some parts even out of date, by the time it is published!
- Science writing is non-emotive, succinct, balanced in description and interpretation. Correct use of technical terminology is important; this creates challenges when writing for a general audience (or, indeed, when teaching) when it can be all too easy to use inappropriate analogies. An example is to draw analogies between terrestrial plants and microalgae, labelling the latter as 'microscopic plants' – this is not correct!
- Reporting in science follows a common structure. This usually comprises the following: **Title** (short); **Abstract** (200-300 word summary of aims, objectives, results, conclusions); **Introduction** (the topic in general, and the specific aims of the work, often with explicit setting

of hypotheses); **Methods and Materials** (reports all information required to repeat the work); **Results** (tables, graphs, photographs, drawings, with allied text to explain salient points); **Discussion** (considers the results, especially set against what others have said); **References** (literature referred to). What was done is described in the past tense; discussions are usually in the current tense.

- d) Interpreting both time-graphs and x-y scatter plots are important skills for all students, and not just for scientists. Photography and line-drawings are also important aspects of communication; producing info-graphics is a particularly useful skill.
- e) Various aspects of the work described here require mathematic manipulations (transforms between units) and use of equations which could also be coded for programmes. Understanding units and using the units is especially important. For example: mgN m^{-3} is a concentration, reporting the amount (mass) of nitrogen per cubic metre of space; $\text{gC (gC)}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$ is a rate, reporting an addition of carbon per 1g of carbon per day.

This teaching resource assumes that you have a reasonable understanding of what plankton are, how and where they grow.

Resources to attain that understanding are available from the following:

[The Plankton Manifesto - A call for Plankton-Based Solutions to address The Triple Planetary Crisis \(biodiversity, climate & pollution\) | UN Global Compact](#)

The target age group for this resource is 13+ years.

Overview

Life in the open water of aquatic ecosystems (ponds, lakes, seas, ocean) depends on growth of planktonic organisms. The plankton comprise organisms, the vast bulk of which are microscopic, that cannot move against water currents. However, many can swim, and migrate up and down (in some instances by altering their buoyancy rather than actively swimming).

The growth of organisms in any ecosystem leads to the production of biomass; in simple terms, biological production is an increase in the weight of the different organisms growing in the ecosystem in a given time. Here, we consider production of planktonic biomass within what is termed the water column.

The water column extends from the surface down to the bottom of that water body. The water depth in ponds and lakes may be of the scale of a few to perhaps tens of metres. However, in the ocean, the total water depth may be many km. Functionally, however, most plankton life depends on sunlight, which enters at the surface but diminishes rapidly with depth. In addition, that sunlight warms the water and warmer water is less dense, floating above colder deeper water. In areas of variable salinity, less-saline fresher water floats above saltier water. A sharp change in temperature is marked by a *thermocline*. A *halocline* describes a salinity gradient. In both instances, the resultant change in water density is described generically as a *pycnocline*. However, such a change is associated not only with changes in water density but importantly it is also associated with a change in the amount of energy in the water that moves around chemicals and small particles such as plankton. The sharp change in energy at the interface between the upper waters, which are mixed by waves, and the less turbulent lower waters, is an *ergocline*. Above the ergocline the water is well mixed, and we term that zone the *mixed layer*.

The subject of this document is the growth of plankton in the mixed layer of the water column. This layer, in the oceans, represents the largest continual ecosystem on Earth.

Learning outcomes

The topic of this document is by its very nature complex and quite unlike the ecology of terrestrial systems that students will have encountered. The subject is also not one that can be easily studied even if the student had ready access to all the required instrumentation and a boat or ship. The route taken here is to exploit simulation models which can be manipulated by the student to allow them to conduct experiments.

To assist in the learning process, the topic has been broken into seven experiments. Students should work through each of these, not progressing until they are comfortable with the current study topic. Like all teaching materials, there are numerous simplifications; attention is drawn to these as the work progresses.

There are multiple learning outcomes to be achieved, and skills to develop, through working through the experiments described here. These skills are tabulated below.

Skill	Exp1	Exp2	Exp3	Exp4	Exp5	Exp6	Exp7
Working with units and transforms	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Diffusion in physics	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Light attenuation			●	●	●	●	●
Light-limited growth with photosynthesis					●	●	●
Microbial physiology and competition						●	●
Ecology and trophic interactions							●
Interpreting time-graphs	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Interpreting x,y scatter graphs						●	●
Experiment design						●	●
Complex, multifactorial analyses					●	●	●

A glossary of important terms is provided.

Near the end of the document there is a section entitled '*What you should have noted*', which will help students check their learning experience.

Introduction

The physical and biological system

Plankton, organisms that support life in the ocean and in lakes, grow in the **water column**. The water column describes a section through the water from the surface (where it meets the atmosphere) down to the bottom (where it meets the seabed or sediment). This environment constrains how life can thrive in aquatic ecosystems. As water covers 2/3rds of the surface of Earth, understanding how the system operates is key to appreciating how life functions over most of the planet.

While typically we may think of fish, turtles, whales, seabirds and similar large animals as key components of aquatic ecosystems, the reality is that the vast bulk (>95%) of the organisms by biomass (weight) are planktonic and microscopic. These organisms can, by definition, only move weakly within the water, although many can alter their buoyancy or actually swim and thus move up (ascend) or down (descend), to or away from the sunlight. Sunlight is critical for the operation of the ecosystem as it provides the major energy input via support for photosynthesis. Light, however, is also dangerous; too much light harms organisms, through causing mutations and other cellular damage, while larger organisms hunt partly by sight.

The water column

A key variable to consider when describing water as an environment is the depth. Water depth spans the surface, where there is light and gas exchange occurs with the atmosphere, and the bottom where the fluid environment meets the solid bottom. However, the water column is not a simple continuum because it is structured in ways that are not immediately obvious.

The physical structure of the water column comes about through changes in water density. That density, described as mass per volume (e.g., Kg L⁻¹), varies as functions of salinity and temperature. Low saline water is less dense and thus floats above more saline, more dense, water. Temperature interactions are rather more complex because water is less dense as a solid (ice) than as a liquid. If it was like a typical compound (the solid being denser than the liquid form) the ocean and lakes would be mainly solid, as ice, with just a thin layer of fluid water on top. Setting aside the fact that water density increases as its temperature decreases below ca. 4°C (depending upon its salinity), at most environmentally relevant temperatures, water is less dense when warmer, and floats above colder more dense water.

Another feature of the water column is that the upper surface is disturbed by the wind. Surface waves have their counterparts as internal waves that move through the water column mixing it vertically. Tidal movements also mix the water column. Further down from the surface, away from the surface waves and nearer bottom where drag decreases water flow rates, this mixing decreases.

However, the density gradients mentioned above also generate a sort of false-bottom within the water column, such that at a certain depth the turbulent mixing in the surface waters becomes insufficient to mix the upper sunlit warmed water with the denser cooler waters lower down.

An interface develops which displays a sharp energy gradient, the **ergocline**. This may take several forms :

Thermocline – an ergocline formed by a sharp temperature gradient. The warmer water is the upper, mixed layer. Thermoclines are the dominant feature defining the ergocline in freshwater lakes and in the ocean.

Halocline – an ergocline formed by a sharp salinity gradient. The less saline water is the upper, mixed layer.

Pycnocline – an ergocline formed as a combination of temperature and salinity that affects water density. Less dense water forms the upper, mixed layer.

The upper zone, above the ergocline, comprises the **mixed layer**, and its vertical extent is termed the **mixed layer depth (MLD)**. The MLD varies depending on location and the time of year. For example, in the mid North Atlantic winter the MLD may be over 200 m, while with warming as the year progresses to summer it shallows to less than 30 m. This change, trapping plankton near the sunlit surface, promotes the operation of planktonic **food webs**, most notably with the development of the **spring bloom**.

The spring bloom describes the growth of photosynthetic plankton that develops following the dark cool winter months. The event may be seen from space as vast areas of the ocean and lake surface waters change colour to (typically) a green-brown.

Storms in the autumn and winter, together with the decreasing heat energy from the sun, result in the deepening of the MLD. Nearer the coast the mixed layer extends to the seabed during the winter. This turbulence, and the decreased sunlight, together create conditions that limit plankton growth.

Mixing of water within the water column is the result of turbulence and it occurs in all directions. However, the direction of most importance in waters away from the coast is vertical. Vertical movement is described by as a **vertical eddy diffusion (VED)**.

In simple terms, eddy diffusion can be considered as a movement of chemicals and small particles; here we consider only vertical movement, though of course there is also movement horizontally. The rate of movement varies with how mixed the water is. If you stir a drop of a food dye into a jug of water, the colour disperses very rapidly; if you place a drop very carefully onto the surface of the water, the colour will disperse slowly. In the mixed layer of a body of water, disturbed by the wind, VED may be ten times faster than that below the ergocline (thermocline, halocline).

[As you will see, from running the simulation experiments, combinations of different values of VED and MLD, coupled with changing light \(with latitude, season, cloud cover\) and nutrients, have profound impacts on plankton growth.](#)

Most plankton production (i.e., organism growth and trophic interactions between organisms), occurs within the MLD. Importantly, key constraints on that production are the supply of light at the surface, and the supply of nutrients that are brought into the lower water column by mixing at the ergocline. This transfer is not only of nutrients but also moves plankton out of the mixed layer and into the lower water column (the sub-mixed layer).

Understanding how processes operate with the MLD is important to gain an understanding not only of how the whole ecosystem operates, but also of why and when different members of the plankton grow as they do.

The biology

The plankton community comprises many 1000's of different species, but at the simplest level we can divide them into **producers** and **consumers**.

Producers

Most plankton producers are photosynthetic, using energy from sunlight to convert CO₂ and various nutrients into biomass. These organisms are **phytoplankton** and **mixoplankton** (collectively, termed **microalgae**); the key difference is that the latter can also act as consumers that eat other organisms to acquire nutrients while the phytoplankton can only use dissolved nutrients. To simplify the studies described here we will consider only phytoplankton producers.

The size of these organisms ranges from 0.001mm to ca. 0.5mm; most (as biomass and numerically) are <0.01mm. There will typically be millions of such organisms per litre of water. They grow with a typical division rate of once per day; under ideal conditions this means that the population size will double every day.

The growth of producers is controlled by the following features:

- i. **light** – light is required for photosynthesis, but too much light is harmful. If possible, against the VED, plankton can position themselves in the water column to optimise light availability. They do this by swimming or by altering their buoyancy.
- ii. **nutrients** – nutrients are required to support growth of the organisms that collectively we describe as its biomass.
- iii. **MLD** – the greater the MLD the more likely it is that producers are in darker waters, unable to photosynthesise at high rates.
- iv. **self shading** – high biomass levels shade out the light; a limit to production is thus set by a combination of light availability at the surface, nutrient availability at a given location within the water column, and the MLD.
- v. **consumers** – these eat the producers, but in doing so they also release nutrients that supports the growth of new generations of producers and also in lessening the effects of self shading.
- vi. **VED** – the higher the rates of vertical eddy diffusion, the less able are the plankton to position themselves in the water column to optimise light or nutrient availability, but the higher the rates of nutrient introduction from below the MLD. The VED also results in an event called **washout**; this is where the growth rate of plankton is less than that of the effective transfer (dilution) rate with waters below the ergocline, and results in the plankton biomass decreasing.

Within 'nutrients' (ii, above), here we will consider only a single type of nutrient, as nitrogen (N). However, we will consider that in two forms, nitrate (NO₃⁻) and ammonium (NH₄⁺). Ammonium is released by consumers as a waste product. Under certain conditions, a group of bacteria convert ammonium through to nitrate; those conditions are especially important in deep dark waters, below the mixed layer. Typically, then, ammonium is made available to support production in the mixed layer while nitrate enters the mixed layer by low rates of mixing across the ergocline.

Consumers

Consumers feed on the producers, or upon other consumers. Here, to simplify matters we will consider only a single type of consumer, as **zooplankton**.

The word 'zooplankton' describes a planktonic organism that eats other organisms. They range from extremely small (0.003mm) single celled organisms (protist zooplankton), through to multicellular animals such as freshwater water fleas, and in oceans to the copepods, krills and sea jellies. We will

define our zooplankton as a protist zooplankton; this has the advantage that its life cycle is (like that of the phytoplankton) is very simple – cells feed, grow, and then once large enough they divide. Some zooplankton can also cannibalise; in the absence of anything else to eat, they eat each other.

As the zooplankton feed they convert part of the biomass of their food into their own biomass; they release the remaining parts that they do not completely digest as faeces (voided waste). They also release carbon dioxide (CO_2) and waste N as ammonium. The voided waste is degraded by bacteria; this is not described in detail in the models used here but it results in a slow conversion of the waste through to more CO_2 and ammonium. Waste is also lost from the mixed layer through the mixing that occurs at the ergocline.

Trophic interactions

The combinations of these interactions between producers and consumers comprise a series of **trophic interactions**. The structure of this simplified **food web** is shown in **Fig.1**. This is the structure of the plankton food web that operates in the upper water column; how this functions under different conditions is the subject of the simulations described here.

Fig.1 Schematic of the simple plankton food web used here. Sunlight (i) and nutrients (ii) support the growth of two types of phytoplankton. Of the nutrients, ammonium is used by preference. The phytoplankton are consumed by zooplankton (iii), with a proportion being voided (iv) as particulate organic matter (POM). Zooplankton respiration results in the conversion of another part of the phytoplankton biomass into ammonium (v) which can be used again by the phytoplankton. The POM is degraded by bacteria, again releasing ammonium (vi); this process is not explicitly described in the model used here. All these processes occur in the upper water column in what is termed the 'mixed layer', separated from the lower water column by an ergocline –

see **Fig.2**. Across the pycnocline there are exchanges of water containing nutrients (vii) and also losses of phytoplankton, zooplankton and POM (viii).

Plankton production and Climate Change

Plankton are at the forefront of climate change events in nature. Population changes can occur rapidly within planktonic systems. This is because of their short generation times; many plankton can reproduce each day, and even the more complex slower growing species have generation times of only a few months. As organisms they cannot, by definition, move out of harms way. If we observe changes in plankton communities at a given location over time (e.g., the development of the spring bloom) we need to understand what is happening, to be able to explain why things are happening as they do. We also need to ascertain whether changes in patterns are due to natural variability (such as with weather) or whether it is showing a response to acute events such as pollution or chronic events such as long term climate change shifts.

Importantly, changes occur in several features of natural systems simultaneously. In some instances changes may perhaps cancel out, but in others the response may be multiplicative which means that responses can be unexpectedly sensitive. In extreme, there can be an event termed a **tipping point**, where a radical change occurs with consequences that proliferate and stabilise the system in a different form to that under which it operated before.

Through the experiments described in this document, the following features may be explored:

- *mixing rates and mixing depth* – storm events, coupled with changes in the warming of surface layers of the ocean, are changing the structure of the water column in which plankton grow. These result in changes to the mixed layer depth (MLD) and in the rates of vertical eddy diffusion (VED) within that mixed layer.
- *shifts in seasonality in abiotic and biotic features* – changes in the weather are altering the timings of plankton growths which would be traditionally associate with spring, summer, autumn and winter. Overlain with the changes in VED and MLD, these are changing the environmental conditions for growth.
- *changes in nutrient loads* – these occur with human activity affecting levels and types of **eutrophication**. These are exacerbated and added to long term trends in changes in MLD and VED that distribute nutrients within the water column and the transfer rates of nutrients in and out of the mixed layer.
- *evolution of growth rates and responses to prey availability* – especially for the microbial plankton, a combination of changes in environmental conditions and the rapid growth of plankton provides scope for evolution to alter maximum growth rate potential. They may also change other features of physiology that may alter the nutritional quality of prey for predators and otherwise affect competitive advantage for different species. Such events affect plankton production. Although the simulation models used here do not consider evolution, you can explore what happens if you change growth rates, susceptibility to high light, motility, changes in palatability to the consumer, and other features either individually or in combination.

Describing events within the Mixed Layer

From the above, it will have become apparent that the movement of water vertically within the water column is a critical determinant of how plankton production can proceed.

Fig.2a gives a schematic showing the mixed layer, between the sunlit surface and the ergocline (typically a thermocline). Below this, extends the sub-mixed layer zone down to the bottom. The ergocline is simply a sharp change in energy in the water. The water above this ergocline has more energy in it, and that energy causes the water to mix. This mixed water zone is thus termed the **mixed layer**, and the depth of water between the surface and the ergocline is the **mixed layer depth (MLD)**.

In reality, of course, the mixed layer is a continuum, so that mathematically we can consider the mixed layer as comprising an infinite number of horizontal slices. Pragmatically, to assist in calculating the mixing processes, let us consider that rather than an infinite number of slices, we divide the MLD into a series of slices each of 1 m depth. Furthermore, we could consider the water column itself as having a surface projection of 1 m².

The blocks of water comprising the mixed layer are thus envisaged as 1 m³; this is shown in **Fig.2b**. The bottom of this column of 1 m³ cubes of water interfaces (at the ergocline) with the sub-mixed layer.

Between each of these cubes there is an exchange of water. In reality the system is far more complex with exchanges not only vertically (in what is termed the z axis) but also horizontally (in the x and y axes). However, if we assume that the x,y exchanges are equal and bi-directional, we can disregard them in this simplification. So, let us then only consider these vertical exchanges; these are associated with **vertical eddy diffusion (VED)**. The exchanges are shown in **Fig.2c** as bidirectional arrows.

Fig.2 Diagrammatic representations of the water column. Panel (a) shows the real situation, with a continuous column; in panel (b) this is simplified to describe the column as a slices visualised here as a series of cubes stacked on each other. In both instances, the column is illuminated by light at the surface, is mixed vertically in the upper portion (bound by an energy gradient, the

ergocline), and has a sub-mixed layer below. Panel (c) shows how in a model we can describe in a simplified form the exchanges of water, nutrients and particles between the slices shown in (b), shown as 1m cubes of water, and the sub-mixed layer. This exchange is driven by vertical eddy diffusion (VED). Note that the VED rates in the mixed layer are greater (hence the thicker green arrow) than they are below the ergocline (hence the thin green arrow exchanging between the final 1m³ and the sub-mixed layer, at the ergocline). Often the biomass and productivity of the plankton within a column is described as an **areal** value, for example as gC m⁻², or gC gC m⁻². Note that the unit of space is of the area m² (not the volume m³) and refers to total value in the water column below an area of 1 m² of the depth defined as the mixed layer (with a unit of m).

Note that the size of those arrows in **Fig.2c** signify the rates of exchange; the exchange between the lowest cube in the mixed layer and the sub-mixed layer is much slower (typically <10% of the mixed layer exchanges).

Now we need to consider how we are going to explore the transfer of materials between these slices of water. For that, we use a **simulation model**.

Simulation models

The way that dissolved and particulate (e.g., nutrients and microscopic organisms, respectively) move within this water column, and the implications for life in aquatic ecosystems, is described in this document in a series of experiments. These experiments make use of **simulation models**.

A simulation model is a representation of the real world that has time as one of its features. Simulations are thus **dynamic**, showing how things like concentration of nutrients and abundance of organisms change over time. In this instance, the simulator show how these features change also with water depth. The models are thus one dimensional (1D) descriptions of the real world. A three dimensional (3D) description would also consider changes geographically with latitude and longitude.

Even as a 1D description, the subject can become highly complex and challenging to interpret. To make the subject easier to understand, the whole study described here is presented as a series of experiments. **These experiments should be undertaken sequentially.**

Each of the foundation experiments (Exp.1 to 5) will take in the region of 15-30 min each to complete in full, though only 5-10 min may be required to gain sufficient oversight before proceeding with the next experiment.

Experiments 6 and 7 have no specific durations as they are sufficiently complex as to provide the base for a student project; an initial 1 hour period would give sufficient initial exposure to the concepts.

The experiments take you through the following concepts and conditions:

- Exp.1 Nutrient diffusion occurs between the sub-mixed layer and the mixed layer, and also within the mixed layer.
- Exp.2 Particle movement occurs within the mixed layer, including the effects of buoyancy in those particles.
- Exp.3 Light is absorbed by pigmented particles within the mixed layer, this being affected by buoyancy of those particles and changing pigment levels.
- Exp.4 Developing from Exp.3, the light conditions can now be set to simulate those at different latitudes (nearer the equator or the North Pole) and also for seasons of the year.
- Exp.5 Developing from Exp.4, now the particles are allowed to grow as a function of the amount of light they receive.

- Exp.6 Developing from Exp.5, now the growing particles are defined as two phytoplankton species, using both light and nutrients to support their growth in competition with each other. Nutrient affects the extent of the growth, and the extent of the growth then affects the amount of light available and hence the rate of growth.
- Exp.7 Developing from Exp.6, now a zooplankton is included so that simple plankton food-web interactions within the mixed layer can be explored. These include impacts of changing nutrient levels, changing water column features, as well as the effects of the time of year and latitude upon the surface sunlight.

All else being equal

The basis of rigorous experiment design is often considered as rooted in altering one thing at a time. By doing this you can have confidence in understanding the contribution that each part plays in the system dynamics. In the real world, such a condition can never be met and many factors change simultaneously. Even if only one abiotic features was altered, such as cloudiness affecting the amount of light at the sea surface, the subsequent dynamics of the growth of photosynthetic organisms with its consumption of nutrients, self-shading of its own growth, interactions with predators and subsequent regeneration of nutrients and alleviation of self-shading, collectively introduce many other factors affecting how ecology functions.

In consequence, system dynamics can never truly function to allow a single factor to be considered at a time. However, with that in mind, it is still sensible to explore logical combinations of factors when manipulating any model.

The important thing is to try and explain why events develop as they do.

In this context it is very important to understand the differences between the activities of the individual and of the population. As examples:

- Individuals may be growing very rapidly but the population of those individuals may be declining; individual growth rates are not to be confused with population growth. The explanation for such an observation may be that removal of individuals, most obviously through predation, prevents the success of individuals from raising the population size.
- Phytoplankton may be nutrient-replete although the concentration of nutrients in the environment may be very low. Here, the explanation is likely that nutrients being released by predators, as waste from digestion and respiration, are immediately recovered by the highly efficient nutrient uptake systems of the phytoplankton.

Running the experiments

The experiments are all run using a simulation application, Powersim Cockpit. This software runs on the MS Windows environment. The application is free and occupies little space.

To download and install the application, please follow instructions in the [Quick Start](#) page, at the start of this document.

When you open the simulation files you will see this ribbon at the top left of the screen.

Of these options, the most important is the zoom option (seen here as '100%'); from this, you should select a zoom value that enables you to best observe all the screen components, or just select 'fit'.

Experiment 1 nutrient diffusion within the mixed layer

For this experiment you will use a simulation model that describes how a chemical (here identified as a N-containing nutrient, 'N') moves within the mixed layer and exchanges with the nutrient within the sub-mixed layer.

The simulator allows you explore how nutrients disperse vertically in the water column within the mixed layer. Here, nutrients enter from the bottom and also at a depth nearer the surface that you can select.

The simulation model for this experiment is named **1D_Exp1.sip**. This operates within a free (no-cost) application **Powersim Cockpit** that needs to be installed on your Windows PC. Please check the **Quick Start** section at the start of this document for details.

You cannot 'break' the model; in the unlikely event that something does go wrong, just reload the simulation file.

Expected duration of this experiment: 15-30 min.

Use the print-screen option to record your simulation outputs; you can then paste the screen copy into another application.

Model interface

The model interface looks like the image below. You may need to alter the zoom magnification.

The simulator allows you to modify various features using sliders. It may help to revisit **Fig.2**.

- Mixed layer depth (**MLD**); this can be altered between 10-50 m.
- Mixed layer vertical eddy diffusion (**VED**) rate; the calmer the mixed layer the slower the value of VED. you may wish to alter it also just to slow down the simulation so you can better observe what is happening. VED can be altered between 10 and 100 $\text{m}^2 \text{d}^{-1}$. The exchange rate between the lowest part of the mixed layer and the sub-mixed layer is set at 10% of the mixed layer VED.
- **N below MLD**; this controls the concentration of nutrient in the water column below the ergocline. Recall that there is an exchange between the bottom of the mixed layer and the sub-mixed layer waters.

- **N input depth**; you can introduce a spike of nutrient into the mixed water layer at a depth you can select between 0 (the surface) and 10 m. You can alter the input depth during the simulation.
- **N input** ; you can alter the concentration of nutrient that the simulation starts with at the depth selected by 'N input depth'. In addition, or instead of, adding a spike of nutrient at the start, you can give a continual input during the simulation. Furthermore, you can alter the depth and input rate (and also the value of 'N below MLD') during the simulation.

Note that clicking above or below the current slider position will make the slider jump to exactly the next numbered position on the slider. This is useful for recreating conditions between tests.

There are two graphs showing the output from the simulation:

- **MLD vs Nutrient**: this shows the concentration of the nutrient in each of the 1 m³ cubes that describe the water column. The surface is at MLD = 1, so that the bottom of the mixed layer is on the right-hand side of the plot on the horizontal (x) axis. The nutrient concentration at each depth is shown on the vertical (y) axis.
- **Time vs Total N**: this shows how the total nutrient in the mixed layer changes over time.

As the simulation proceeds the output of the plots will change. The axes on the plots are self-scaling at the end of the simulation, but you may wish to press 'F9' on your keyboard during the simulation to better observe what is happening.

Note that the MLD slider only works before the simulation starts, while you can alter the others during the simulation.

Start by resetting the simulation, by pressing **Ctrl+R**. Then make your selections using the sliders.

Start a simulation by pressing **Ctrl+space**.

You can **pause the simulation** at any time by pressing **Ctrl+space** again; un-pause by repeating **Ctrl+space**.

To **reset the simulation**, to start a new run, again press **Ctrl+R**.

Things to explore

Note that the sliders will stay in their position between simulations; you can thus experiment by altering one factor at a time, which is the best way to conduct the initial stages of any scientific experiment.

In all instances try and explain why you are observing the changes in the plots.

- Set **N input** to zero, set a deep **MLD**, and a slow **VED rate**. See what happens in the simulation using different values of **N below MLD**.
- Repeat, but changing **N below MLD** and/or **VED rate** during the simulation.
- Now, set **N below MLD** to zero, and introduce a **N spike** at a **N input depth** of your choice.
- Repeat with different values for **N input depth**, and different **VED rate** values.
- Combine the **N input** and **N below MLD** experiments described above, and repeat with different **MLD** and **VED rate** values.

Try to summarize what you observe.

Try and place these observations in an ecological context. For example:

- As time moves from spring to summer, the MLD may become shallower and calmer (i.e., the VED rate will also decrease)
- The spike addition could be considered as a pollution event; how quickly may it disperse under different conditions?

Caveats

Recall that simulations are always simplifications of reality. It is important to consider how your understanding of real events may be affected by such simplifications. The same, incidentally, applies to all studies of natural systems, and not just to simulations.

There is no change in MLD during the simulation. Here, the simulation duration is 20d. It is unlikely that the MLD will remain unchanged over this period. You can, however, adjust VED.

It is unlikely that a nutrient addition would be made in water conditions like this. It is more likely that such an addition would occur near land where water current (including tidal flows) would add to the turbulence.

Experiment 2 particle movement

You should have completed **Experiment 1** before proceeding.

For this experiment you will use a simulation model that describes how inert particles (described here as biomass) move within the mixed layer and exchanges with the sub-mixed layer.

The simulator allows you to explore how particles disperse vertically in the water column, affected by their own buoyancy (ascent or descent rate) as well as by the vertical mixing.

The simulation model for this experiment is named **1D_Exp2.sip**. This operates within a free (no-cost) application **Powersim Cockpit** that needs to be installed on your Windows PC. Please check the **Quick Start** section at the start of this document for details.

You cannot 'break' the model; in the unlikely event that something does go wrong, just reload the simulation file.

Expected duration of this experiment: 15-30 min.

Use the print-screen option to record your simulation outputs; you can then paste the screen copy into another application.

Model interface

The model interface looks like the image below. You may need to alter the zoom magnification.

The simulator allows you to modify various following features using sliders. It may help to revisit **Fig.2**.

- Mixed layer depth (**MLD**); this can be altered between 10-50 m.
- Mixed layer vertical eddy diffusion (**VED**) rate; the calmer the mixed layer the slower this will be but here you may wish to alter it also just to slow down the simulation so you can better observe what is happening. VED can be altered between 10 and 100 $\text{m}^2 \text{d}^{-1}$. The exchange rate between the lowest part of the mixed layer and the sub-mixed layer is set at 10% of the mixed layer VED.

- **Ascent rate**; this controls the rate at which the particles rise (ascend due to swimming, or float due to positive buoyancy) or conversely sink (descend, negative buoyancy). Note that a negative ascent rate is a descent; the red line on the slider indicates the neutral buoyancy value of a zero ascent rate.
- **Spike depth**; introduce a spike of the particles into the mixed water layer at a depth of your choice between 0 (the surface) and 10 m. This event occurs at the start of the simulation.

Note that clicking above or below the current slider position will make the slider jump to exactly the next numbered position on the slider. This is useful for recreating conditions between tests.

There are two graphs showing the output from the simulation:

- **MLD vs Biomass**: this shows the concentration of the particle biomass in each of the 1 m³ cubes that describe the water column. The surface is at MLD = 1, so that the bottom of the mixed layer is on the right-hand side of the plot (x-axis). The biomass concentration at each depth is shown on the vertical y-axis.
- **Time vs Total biomass**: this shows how the total biomass in the mixed layer changes over time.

The axes on the plots are self-scaling at the end of the simulation, but you may wish to press 'F9' on your keyboard during the simulation to better observe what is happening.

Note that some of the sliders only work before the simulation starts (MLD, spike depth), while you can alter the others during the simulation.

Start off by resetting the simulation, by pressing **Ctrl+R**. Then make your selections using the sliders.

Start a simulation by pressing **Ctrl+space**.

You can **pause the simulation** at any time by pressing **Ctrl+space**; un-pause by repeating **Ctrl+space**.

To **reset the simulation**, to start a new run, press **Ctrl+R**.

Things to explore

Note that the sliders will stay in their position between simulations; you can thus experiment altering one factor at a time, which is the best way to conduct the initial stages of any scientific experiment.

In all instances try and explain why you are observing the changes in the plots.

- With a slow **VED rate** and deep **MLD**, set the **Ascent rate** at zero (marked by the red line), with a shallow **Spike depth**.
- Repeat with a deep **Spike depth**.
- Repeat both the steps above but setting a maximum **Ascent rate**.
- Repeat both the first two steps again, but with a minimum **Ascent rate** (i.e. negative).
- Explore these events again with shallower **MLD**, and faster **VED rate**.

Try to summarize what you observe.

Try and place these observations in an ecological context. For example:

- As time moves from spring to summer, the MLD may become shallower and calmer (VED rate will decrease)

- The spike addition could be considered as a pollution event of inert particles (microplastics, for example); how quickly may that addition disperse under different conditions?
- What do you think might happen if the particles were not inert, but they either decayed (for example, particles of sewage), or grew (for example, phytoplankton)?

Caveats

Recall that simulations are always simplifications of reality. It is important to consider how your understanding of real events may be affected by such simplifications. The same, incidentally, applies to all studies of natural systems, and not just to simulations.

There is no change in MLD during the simulation. Here, the simulation duration is 20d. It is unlikely that the MLD will remain unchanged over this period. You can, however, adjust VED.

It is unlikely that an addition of inert particles would be made in water conditions like this. It is more likely that such an addition would occur near land where water current (including tidal flows) would add to the turbulence.

Experiment 3 pigmented particle movement and light

You should have completed Experiments 1 and 2 before proceeding.

For this experiment you will use a simulation model that describes how inert but coloured particles of biomass move within the mixed layer and exchange with the sub-mixed layer.

The simulation allows you to explore what happens to the amount of light that penetrates through the mixed layer. The light is greatest at the surface (MLD block 1, on the left side of the plots), but is absorbed by coloured particles as the light passes down to the bottom of the mixed layer.

Why is this important?

It is important because the growth of photosynthetic plankton (**microalgae**) depends on the amount of light they receive and then capture. They capture light using pigments such as **chlorophyll**. However, every photon of light captured by the pigments in a microalga in the upper water column is not then available for those microalgae below it in the water column.

Even without microalgae in the water column, light is absorbed by chemicals in the water so that light gradually decreases as it passes down from the surface. Near land, for example, there is often coloured dissolved organic matter (cDOM) formed of tannins from decaying vegetation.

The simulation model for this experiment is named [1D_Exp3.sip](#). This operates within a free (no-cost) application **Powersim Cockpit** that needs to be installed on your Windows PC. Please check the [Quick Start](#) section at the start of this document for details.

You cannot 'break' the model; in the unlikely event that something does go wrong, just reload the simulation file.

Expected duration of this experiment: 15-30 min.

Use the print-screen option to record your simulation outputs; you can then paste the screen copy into another application.

Model interface

The model interface looks like the image below. You may need to alter the zoom magnification.

The simulator allows you to modify various following features using sliders. It may help to revisit **Fig.2**.

Mixed layer depth (**MLD**); this can be altered between 10-50 m.

- **Mixed layer vertical eddy diffusion (VED) rate**; the calmer the mixed layer the slower this will be but here you may wish to alter it also just to slow down the simulation so you can better observe what is happening. VED can be altered between 10 and 100 m² d⁻¹. The exchange rate between the lowest part of the mixed layer and the sub-mixed layer is set at 10% of the mixed layer VED.
- **Ascent rate**; this controls the rate at which the particles rise (ascend by swimming, or float with positive buoyancy) or conversely sink (descend, negative buoyancy). Note that a negative ascent rate is a descent; the red line indicates a zero ascent rate (neutral buoyancy).
- **Spike depth**; introduce a spike of the particles into the mixed water layer at a depth of your choice between 0 (the surface) and 10 m. This event occurs at the start of the simulation.
- **ChlC**; this allows you to alter the colour of the particles. To be specific, here you alter the ratio of the photosynthetic pigment chlorophyll (Chl) to the C-biomass (C). Thus, the units of **ChlC** are gChl g⁻¹C. The highest value you can set is 0.08; this means that 1 g of particle carbon is associated with 0.08 g of chlorophyll, which makes it very green. A low value will make it pale, but for a photosynthetic organism that also means that it would not be able to capture so many photons in low light levels.

Note that clicking above or below the current slider position will make the slider jump to exactly the next numbered position on the slider. This is useful for recreating conditions between tests.

There are three graphs showing the output from the simulation:

- **MLD vs Biomass and Chl**: this shows the concentration (abundance) of the particle biomass in each of the 1 m³ cubes that describe the water column, and also the concentration of the pigment chlorophyll (Chl). The surface is at MLD = 1, so that the bottom of the mixed layer is on

the right-hand side of the plot. The biomass and Chl concentrations at each depth are shown on the vertical axis. Note that the units for biomass and for Chl are different. Also, to allow the data to be plotted on the same graph, the biomass values have been converted from C to N assuming 1gC is associated with 0.15gN in the biomass.

- **MLD vs light:** this shows the light that would be received by the biomass in each of the 1 m³ cubes that describe the water column. The surface is at MLD = 1, so that the bottom of the mixed layer is on the right-hand side of the plot. The amount of light is highest at the surface and decreases with depth as a consequence of absorption by the water in each cube of water but mainly by absorption by the Chl associated with the biomass in each cube. A lot of biomass, and especially if that biomass has a high Chl:C value, results in a lot of light being removed in that cube (i.e., at that depth), making the water below it darker. The units for light are $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; this is a count of light packages ('photons') received by every square metre per second. A value of around 2000 is the amount of noon-day light received at the water surface under a cloudless sky.
- **Time vs Total biomass:** this shows how the total biomass in the mixed layer changes over time.

As the simulation proceeds the output of the plots will change. Because the axes on the plots are self-scaling, you may need to press 'F9' on your keyboard during the simulation to better observe what is happening.

Note that some of the sliders only work before the simulation starts (MLD, spike depth), while you can alter the others during the simulation.

Start off by resetting the simulation, by pressing **Ctrl+R**. Then make your selections using the sliders.

Start a simulation by pressing **Ctrl+space**.

You can **pause the simulation** at any time by pressing **Ctrl+space**; un-pause by repeating **Ctrl+space**.

To **reset the simulation**, to start a new run, press **Ctrl+R**.

Things to explore

Note that the sliders will stay in their position between simulations; you can thus experiment altering one factor at a time, which is the best way to conduct the initial stages of any scientific experiment.

In all instances try and explain why you are observing the changes in the plots.

- With a slow **VED rate** and deep **MLD**, set the **Ascent rate** at zero (marked by the red line), with a shallow **Spike depth**. Use a high **ChlC** value.
- Repeat with a deep **Spike depth**.
- Repeat both the steps above but with a low **ChlC**.
- Repeat all the above with a maximum **Ascent rate**.
- And now repeat all the above with a minimum (i.e., negative) **Ascent rate**.
- Explore these events again with shallower **MLD**, and faster **VED rate**.

Try to summarize what you observe.

Try and place these observations in an ecological context. For example:

- How does the light in the water column change with your settings and as the simulation progresses.
- How can you minimize the loss of the biomass (plot of time vs total biomass) and maximise the amount of light in the water column (plot of MLD vs light)?

What do you think might happen if the biomass grew rather than being inert? (You will explore that in Experiment 5).

Caveats

Recall that simulations are always simplifications of reality. It is important to consider how your understanding of real events may be affected by such simplifications. The same, incidentally, applies to all studies of natural systems, and not just to simulations.

There is no change in MLD during the simulation. Here, the simulation duration is 20d. It is unlikely that the MLD will remain unchanged over this period. You can, however, adjust VED.

The biomass would, in reality, grow or die. In addition, the level of pigmentation (set by Chl:C) would vary over time as the organisms were exposed to more light (Chl:C would decrease) or to darkness (Chl:C increases to a maximum). As you will have realised, combinations of high biomass and high Chl:C in a given block of water has a big impact on the amount of light in the water below that block.

Experiment 4 pigmented particle movement and geolocated seasonal light

You should have completed Experiments 1, 2 and 3 before proceeding.

For this experiment you will use a simulation model that describes how inert but coloured particles of biomass move within the mixed layer and exchange with the sub-mixed layer. Unlike Experiment 3, where light was fixed, here the light is described according to a selected latitude and month of the year.

The simulation model for this experiment is named [1D_Exp4.sip](#). This operates within a free (no-cost) application **Powersim Cockpit** that needs to be installed on your Windows PC. Please check the [Quick Start](#) section at the start of this document for details.

You cannot 'break' the model; in the unlikely event that something does go wrong, just reload the simulation file.

Expected duration of this experiment: 15-30 min.

Use the print-screen option to record your simulation outputs; you can then paste the screen copy into another application.

This simulation is similar to the one you used in Experiment 3, with similar controls. The difference is in the description of the light.

Why is this important?

The availability of light changes with the location on Earth, and the day of the year. In the Northern hemisphere, which has latitudes between 0° (the equator) and 90°N (the North Pole), the day light period (dawn to dusk) increases from a minimum at 21st December to a maximum at 21st June. The amount of light at noon (when the sun is highest in the sky) also increases. Although these changes are not very obvious at the equator, they become very obvious at latitudes greater than ca. 60°. This has an important impact on the availability of light that supports plankton photosynthesis and hence the plankton production that supports all of the other aquatic organisms in the water column.

Model interface

The model interface looks like the image below. You may need to alter the zoom magnification.

The simulator allows you to modify various features using sliders. For some of these, it may help to revisit **Fig.2**.

- **Latitude**; this geolocates the simulation between 0° (equator) and 80°N (inside the Arctic circle).
- **Month**; this sets the start day of the simulation. Together with Latitude, this governs the amount of light and the day-night periodicity.
- Mixed layer depth (**MLD**); this can be altered between 10-50 m.
- Mixed layer vertical eddy diffusion (**VED**) rate; the calmer the mixed layer the slower depth this will be but here you may wish to alter it also just to slow down the simulation so you can better observe what is happening. VED can be altered between 10 and 100 m² d⁻¹. The exchange rate between the lowest part of the mixed layer and the sub-mixed layer is set at 10% of the mixed layer VED.
- **Ascent rate**; this controls the rate at which the particles rise (ascend, swim or float with positive buoyancy) or conversely sink (descend, negative buoyancy). Note that a negative ascent rate is a descent; the red line indicates a zero ascent rate (neutral buoyancy).
- **Spike depth**; introduce a spike of the particles into the mixed water layer at a depth of your choice between 0 (the surface) and 10 m. This event occurs at the start of the simulation.
- **ChlC**; this allows you to alter the colour of the particles. To be specific, here you alter the ratio of the photosynthetic pigment chlorophyll (Chl) to the C-biomass (C). Thus, the units of **ChlC** are gChl g⁻¹C. The highest value you can set is 0.08; this means that 1 g of particle carbon is associated with 0.08 g of chlorophyll, which makes it very green. A low value will make it pale, but for the organism that also means that it is not able to capture so many photons at low light levels.

Note that clicking above or below the current slider position will make the slider jump to exactly the next numbered position on the slider. This is useful for recreating conditions between tests.

There are four graphs showing the output from the simulation:

- **MLD vs Biomass and Chl:** this shows the concentration (abundance) of the particle biomass in each of the 1 m³ cubes that describe the water column, and also the concentration of the pigment chlorophyll (Chl). The surface is at MLD = 1, so that the bottom of the mixed layer is on the right-hand side of the plot. The biomass and Chl concentrations at each depth are shown on the vertical axis. Note that the units for biomass and for Chl are different. Also, to allow the data to be plotted on the same graph, the biomass values have been converted from C to N assuming 1 gC is associated with 0.15 gN in the biomass.
- **MLD vs light:** this shows the light that would be received by the biomass in each of the 1 m³ cubes that describe the water column. The surface is at MLD = 1, so that the bottom of the mixed layer is on the right-hand side of the plot. The amount of light is highest at the surface and decreases with depth as a consequence of absorption by the water in each cube of water and also by absorption by the Chl associated with the biomass in each cube. A lot of biomass, and especially of that biomass has a high Chl:C value, results in a lot of light being removed in that cube (i.e., at that depth), making the water below it darker. The units for light are $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; this is a count of light packages ('photons') received by every square metre per second. A value of around 2000 is the amount of noon-day light received at the water surface under a cloudless sky.
- **Time vs Total biomass:** this shows how the total biomass in the mixed layer changes over time.
- **Time vs Light:** this shows both the surface light and the average light (avgE) within the whole water column (over the depth described by **MLD**). The value of avgE will change as the surface light changes and also as the biomass concentration (abundance) and its pigment content (Chl) changes.

As the simulation proceeds the output of the plots will change. Because the axes on the plots are self-scaling, you may need to press 'F9' on your keyboard during the simulation to better observe what is happening.

Note that some of the sliders only work before the simulation starts (MLD, spike depth), while you can alter the others during the simulation. You can even alter the latitude and date during the simulation.

Start off by resetting the simulation, by pressing **Ctrl+R**. Then make your selections using the sliders.

Start a simulation by pressing **Ctrl+space**.

You can **pause the simulation** at any time by pressing **Ctrl+space**; un-pause by repeating **Ctrl+space**.

To **reset the simulation**, to start a new run, press **Ctrl+R**.

Things to explore

Note that the sliders will stay in their position between simulations; you can thus experiment altering one factor at a time, which is the best way to conduct the initial stages of any scientific experiment.

In all instances try and explain why you are observing the changes in the plots.

- Select a low **Latitude** (ca. below 20°N) and a winter **Month** (within the range of December-February; i.e., use a month setting of 12, 1 or 2)
- With a slow **VED rate** and deep **MLD**, set the **Ascent rate** at zero (marked by the red line), with a shallow **Spike depth**. Use a high **ChlC** value. Run the simulation and see what happens.
- Repeat with a deep **Spike depth**.

- Repeat both the steps above but with a low **ChlC**.
- Repeat all the above with a maximum **Ascent rate**.
- And now repeat all the above with a minimum (i.e., negative) **Ascent rate**.
- Explore these events again with shallower **MLD**, and faster **VED rate**, as you wish.
- Repeat the above but with a summer **Month**.
- Repeat it all again using a high **Latitude** (ca. higher than 60°N), with winter (months 11, 12, 1, 2) and then summer (months 5, 6, 7, 8) **Month** values.

Try to summarize what you observe.

Try and place these observations in an ecological context. For example:

- How does the light in the water column change with your settings and as the simulation progresses.
- How can you minimize the loss of the biomass (plot of time vs total biomass) and maximise the amount of light in the water column (plot of MLD vs light)?

What do you think might happen if the biomass grew rather than being inert?

What do you think might happen if the biomass actively migrated up and down in the water column to balance obtaining light at the surface and nutrients entering the mixed layer at the ergocline?

Caveats

Recall that simulations are always simplifications of reality. It is important to consider how your understanding of real events may be affected by such simplifications. The same, incidentally, applies to all studies of natural systems, and not just to simulations.

There is no change in MLD during the simulation. Here, the simulation during is 20d. It is unlikely that the MLD will remain unchanged over this period; that is especially so during the winter! You can, however, adjust VED.

The biomass would, in reality, grow or die. In addition, the level of pigmentation (set by Chl:C) would vary over time as the organisms were exposed to more light (Chl:C would decrease) or to darkness (Chl:C increases to a maximum). As you will have realised, combinations of high biomass and high Chl:C in a given block of water has a big impact on the amount of light in the water below that block.

There is an obvious facet of the light system which is not included here, namely the effect of cloud cover. The simulation assumes a clear sky, with no clouds.

Experiment 5 Light-limited growth in the water column with geolocated seasonal light

You should have completed Experiments 1, 2, 3 and 4 before proceeding.

For this experiment you will use a simulation model that describes organism (microalgal) growth within the mixed layer. Like Experiment 4, here the light is described according to the selected latitude and month of the year. Unlike the situation in Experiment 4, now the particles will grow and can react to environmental conditions affecting light availability.

This simulation is similar to the one you used in Experiment 4, with similar controls. **The difference is that now the particles can grow.**

You should have noticed from Experiments 2-4 that the total particle or biomass decreased during the simulation. Irrespective of the buoyancy and the vertical eddy diffusion rate, slowly the amount of biomass decreased as it was lost by mixing into the sub-mixed layer. You should also have noted, from Experiment 1, that the nutrient level in the mixed layer attained a balance between the levels above and below the ergocline.

In short, nutrients enters the surface mixed layer from deep water, while biomass in the surface exits the mixed layer into deep water. It may help to revisit **Fig.2** to better appreciate these details. All of this, and more, will be the subject for Experiment 6. But first, you need to better appreciate the way that biomass growth occurs when it is limited by light only.

The simulation model for this experiment is named [1D_Exp5.sip](#). This operates within a free (no-cost) application **Powersim Cockpit** that needs to be installed on your Windows PC. Please check the [Quick Start](#) section at the start of this document for details.

You cannot 'break' the model; in the unlikely event that something does go wrong, just reload the simulation file.

Expected duration of this experiment: 15-30 min.

Use the print-screen option to record your simulation outputs; you can then paste the screen copy into another application.

Light-limited growth

In the simulation, the growth of the biomass is a function of the amount of light received. The amount of light received by the biomass in each slice of the water column is affected by the amount entering the water column (which varies with latitude and date), and the time of day. It is then affected, as you will have noted from Experiments 3 and 4, by light absorption within the water column. Once the light reaches the biomass another factor comes into play - the relationship between the amount of light and growth is not linear, but it is curvi-linear (**Fig.3**).

The growth of a microalgae depends on how much light energy it can capture. It captures light using pigments such as chlorophyll. If it contains more chlorophyll (i.e., Chl:C is higher) then it can grow faster at low light levels. As you will see from the simulations, however, there is a trade-off between having a high versus a low Chl:C.

The relationships shown in **Fig.3** between light and photosynthesis shows that the growth curve saturates; here, above a light value of ca. $300 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, there is no further increase in the

growth rate. Photosynthesis, which drives growth, has units of d^{-1} ; what that actually means is revealed by the full units, which would be for example $gC\ g^{-1}C\ d^{-1}$. These units, written formally look like this:

$$\frac{gC}{gC} \cdot \frac{1}{d}$$

In words, this says that per g of C as biomass, another unit of g of C is added per day. The gC/gC cancel out, leaving us with units of $1/d$, or d^{-1} .

Fig.3 Light-growth curve relationship. This is shown for two instances, with different values of Chl:C. Note that the version for microalgae containing more chlorophyll (ChlC=0.06) shows more growth at low light. The inset shows the growth rates at light levels down to darkness. The values go negative when the rate of photosynthesis no longer exceeds that for respiration. The point where the curve crosses the 0 value for growth is the 'compensation point'; photosynthesis balances respiration, with the organism neither growing nor dying. Units for light are $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, and for growth are d^{-1} (see text for discussion).

A growth rate of $0.693\ d^{-1}$ (which is natural log 2, or $\text{Ln}(2)$, d^{-1}) gives a doubling of biomass every day. If the growth rate is 0.3465 (i.e. $0.693/2$) d^{-1} , then it takes 2 days for the biomass to double. Growth for an organism is balance of gains and losses. For a photosynthetic organism (as here), there is a cost due to respiration. At very low light (as shown in the inset to **Fig.3**), the growth rate is actually negative and the organism will die.

In continuous light, photosynthesis is continuous, and hence microalgal growth is continuous. Growth proceeds in a fashion rather like a compound interest rate on savings in a bank; ever bit made helps make the next bit. In nature, light is not continuous except in the polar summer, so growth starts and stops during each day.

The typical maximum growth rate for microalgae is a division per day, but the actual growth rate will vary depending on how much light is being received and also the amount of time during the day that light is actually available (i.e., the day-light period). You will have seen from Experiment 4 how the daily light availability changes; if you consider that availability would interact with the curve shown in **Fig.3**, you can probably start to appreciate the different growth conditions experienced by microalgal plankton living in surface waters versus those growing lower in the mixed layer.

Model interface

The model interface looks like the image below. You may need to alter the zoom magnification.

The simulator allows you to modify various following features using sliders. For some of these, it may help to revisit **Fig.2**.

- **Latitude**; this geolocates the simulation between 0° (equator) and 80°N (inside the Arctic circle).
- **Month**; this sets the start day of the simulation. Together with Latitude, this governs the amount of light and the day-night periodicity.
- Mixed layer depth (**MLD**); this can be altered between 10-50 m.
- Mixed layer vertical eddy diffusion (**VED**) rate; the calmer the mixed layer the slower this will be but here you may wish to alter it also just to slow down the simulation so you can better observe what is happening. VED can be altered between 10 and 100 m² d⁻¹. The exchange rate between the lowest part of the mixed layer and the sub-mixed layer is set at 10% of the mixed layer VED.
- **Ascent rate**; this controls the rate at which nutrient-replete plankton rise (ascend, swimming or floating with positive buoyancy) or conversely sink (descend, negative buoyancy). Note that a negative ascent rate is a descent; the red line indicates a zero ascent rate (neutral buoyancy). For phytoplankton, ascent supports the exploitation of light for photosynthesis (which is higher at the surface).
- **Spike depth**; introduce a spike of the microalgae into the mixed water layer at a depth of your choice between 0 (the surface) and 10 m. This event occurs at the start of the simulation.
- **ChlC**; this allows you to alter the colour of the microalgae. To be specific, here you alter the ratio of the photosynthetic pigment chlorophyll (Chl) to the C-biomass (C). Thus, the units of **ChlC** are gChl g⁻¹C. The highest value you can set is 0.08; this means that 1g of particle carbon is associated with 0.08 g of chlorophyll, which makes it very green. A low value will make it pale, but for the organism that also means that it is not able to capture so many photons at low light levels (see **Fig.3**).
- **Pmax**; this allows you to control the maximum rate of photosynthesis (d⁻¹) and hence the maximum growth rate of the microalgal biomass. The actual growth rate depends on the light availability and the value of Chl:C. Nutrients are assumed to be non-limiting; you will explore the effects of nutrient limitation in Experiment 6.

Note that clicking above or below the current slider position will make the slider jump to exactly the next numbered position on the slider. This is useful for recreating conditions between tests.

There are four graphs showing the output from the simulation:

- **MLD vs Biomass and Chl:** this shows the concentration (abundance) of the particle biomass in each of the 1 m^3 cubes that describe the water column, and also the concentration of the pigment chlorophyll (Chl). The surface is at $\text{MLD} = 1$, so that the bottom of the mixed layer is on the right-hand side of the plot. The biomass and Chl concentrations at each depth are shown on the vertical axis. Note that the units for biomass and for Chl are different. Also, to allow the data to be plotted on the same graph, the biomass values have been converted from C to N assuming 1 gC is associated with 0.15 gN in the biomass.
- **MLD vs light:** this shows the light that would be received by the biomass in each of the 1 m^3 cubes that describe the water column. The surface is at $\text{MLD} = 1$, so that the bottom of the mixed layer is on the right-hand side of the plot. The amount of light is highest at the surface and decreases with depth as a consequence of absorption by the water in each cube of water and also by absorption by the Chl associated with the biomass in each cube. A lot of biomass, and especially of that biomass has a high ChlC value, results in a lot of light being removed in that cube (i.e., at that depth), making the water below it darker. The units for light are $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; this is a count of light packages ('photons') received by every square metre per second. A value of around 2000 is the amount of noon-day light received at the water surface under a cloudless sky.
- **Time vs Total biomass:** this shows how the total biomass in the mixed layer changes over time.
- **Time vs Light:** this shows both the surface light and the average light (avgE) within the whole water column (over the depth described by **MLD**). The value of avgE will change as the surface light changes and also as the biomass concentration (abundance) and its pigment content (Chl) changes.

As the simulation proceeds the output of the plots will change. Because the axes on the plots are self-scaling, and the biomass (and thence the Chl value) increases continuously, you will need to repeatedly press 'F9' on your keyboard during the simulation to better observe what is happening.

Note that some of the sliders only work before the simulation starts (MLD, spike depth), while you can alter the others during the simulation. You can even alter the latitude and date during the simulation.

Start off by resetting the simulation, by pressing **Ctrl+R**. Then make your selections using the sliders.

Start a simulation by pressing **Ctrl+space**.

You can **pause the simulation** at any time by pressing **Ctrl+space**; un-pause by repeating **Ctrl+space**.

To **reset the simulation**, to start a new run, press **Ctrl+R**.

Things to explore

Note that the sliders will stay in their position between simulations; you can thus experiment altering one factor at a time, which is the best way to conduct the initial stages of any scientific experiment.

In all instances try and explain why you are observing the changes in the plots.

- Select a low **Latitude** (ca. below 20°N) and winter **Month** (within the range of December-February; month settings 12, 1 or 2)
- Set **Pmax** at a high value
- With a slow **VED rate** and deep **MLD**, set the **Ascent rate** at zero (marked by the red line), with a shallow **Spike depth**. Use a high **ChlC** value.
- Repeat with a deep **Spike depth**.
- Repeat both the steps above but with a low **ChlC** – note in particular how the **MLD vs light** and the **time vs total biomass** plots develop!
- Repeat all the above with a maximum **Ascent rate**.
- And now repeat all the above with a minimum (i.e., negative) **Ascent rate**.
- Explore these events again with shallower **MLD**, and faster **VED rate**, as you wish.
- Repeat the above but with a summer **Month**.
- Repeat it all again using a high **Latitude** (ca. high than 60°N), with winter and summer **Month** values.
- And repeat using a lower **Pmax**

Try to summarize what you observe.

Try and place these observations in an ecological context. For example:

- From **Fig.3**, having a higher ChlC appears beneficial, but does it work out like that in the simulation? Explain your reasoning.
- What situations do you think would affect your explanations? For example, what might happen if there were two microalgal species growing in competition in the same water column, one with a high Chl:C and one with a low Chl:C? What about the effect of changing light with weather (here the light assumes cloudless days)?

Finally, what might happen if something other than just light was involved in controlling microalgal growth. For example, nutrient limitation or the activity of predators (i.e., zooplankton)? In thinking over that question, you may wish to recall that the action of predators not only removes prey (here, it would remove the microalgal biomass) but it would release nutrients back into the system (see **Fig.1**).

Caveats

Recall that simulations are always simplifications of reality. It is important to consider how your understanding of real events may be affected by such simplifications. The same, incidentally, applies to all studies of natural systems, and not just to simulations.

There is no change in MLD during the simulation. Here, the simulation during is 20d. It is unlikely that the MLD will remain unchanged over this period. You can, however, adjust VED.

There is an obvious facet of the light system which is not included here, namely the effect of cloud cover. The simulation assumes a clear sky, with no clouds.

The most important caveat is simply that growth could never develop like this, unlimited by nutrient availability. Even if a vast excess of nutrients was supplied, other events would develop to halt growth. One of those events would be a change in the pH (acidity) of the water; as photosynthesis occurs CO₂ is removed from the water, which raises the pH to levels that are lethal to microalgae. The effects of nutrient limitation are explored in Experiment 6.

Experiment 6 Nutrient-Light-limited growth of competing phytoplankton communities in the water column

You should have completed Experiments 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 before proceeding.

For this experiment you will use a simulation model that describes organism (microalgal) growth within the mixed layer. Like Experiments 4 and 5, here the light is described according to the selected latitude and month of the year.

The simulation model for this experiment is named [1D_Exp6.sip](#). This operates within a free (no-cost) application **Powersim Cockpit** that needs to be installed on your Windows PC. Please check the [Quick Start](#) section at the start of this document for details.

You cannot 'break' the model; in the unlikely event that something does go wrong, just reload the simulation file.

Expected duration of this experiment: 60+ min.

Use the print-screen option to record your simulation outputs; you can then paste the screen copy into another application.

WARNING – this experiment represents a significant increase in complexity over the previous experiments. It is easy to become disorientated when confronted with so many permutations to explore.

Remember, that a simulation, even a very complex one, is much simpler than the real world. As with working in the real world, be methodical in how you approach the task. Do not feel that you need to alter everything; if in doubt set sliders to a mid position while you explore just a few variables.

This activity builds on those in the previous Experiments but now introduces a second phytoplankton to compete for light and nutrients.

The model supporting this experiment has many more options than those available in the previous Experiments. Indeed, the permutations available would make this activity one that is open-ended and well suited to student project work extending over many hours.

Before proceeding, it is worth considering the types of competition that may be considered between the phytoplankton.

Competition between phytoplankton for light and nutrients

In this experiment various factors controlling phytoplankton growth can be changed, as in Experiment 5. The three big advances in this simulation are:

- 1) growth is now nutrient limited in addition to being limited by light.
- 2) there are two phytoplankton described, and these compete for resources (light and nutrients).
- 3) high light levels damage photosynthetic tissues so that the curve form shown in **Fig.3** actually often reveals a decreasing rate of growth at high light.

Only one type of nutrient, nitrogen (N), is described here. In reality, phytoplankton also need other nutrients, most notably as P, Fe, and some require large amounts of silicate (Si).

Although only N is described, it is available in two different dissolved inorganic forms, namely as nitrate (NO_3^-) and ammonium (NH_4^+). The role of these in plankton ecology has been mentioned in the **Introduction**. The only factor of importance for the simulations presented here is that ammonium is the preferred form of dissolved inorganic N (i.e., it is consumed first).

The model itself also has more factors that can be changed and these will alter the **competitive advantage** of one phytoplankton over the other.

What does **competitive advantage** actually mean?

In any ecosystem there are only so many resources. Some of these will be shared with very many organisms (such as major nutrient types, such as nitrate, ammonium, phosphate and iron), while others may be shared with fewer organisms (such as vitamins, or prey for a given predator). In the description given here for two phytoplankton, there are only 2 resources, namely light and nutrient as N. However, even though there are only two resources, competition for them is more complex than it may first appear.

Firstly, the use of these resources interact; the more nutrients that are present, the greater is the potential biomass that grows and accumulates, and that biomass itself attenuates (cuts out) light. This is associated by an event called **self-shading**; the same event can be seen in a forest where the tree canopy shades the plants on the forest floor.

Secondly, if the phytoplankton have different abilities to alter their position in the water column, then they interact in another way. An organism closer to the surface has more access to light, but less to the nutrient that is mixed into the mixed layer at the ergocline (see **Fig.2**), and vice versa. If the phytoplankton can move quickly enough, such that they collect light during the day and move down to collect nutrients at night (a process called 'diel vertical migration') then there is scope for further interactions.

There are many factors that affect competition between phytoplankton. Of these, the only factors available here for you to explore are:

- **maximum growth rate** – the higher this value, the faster the organism can grow. The downside is that (all else being equal) a higher nutrient concentration is required to saturate demand; slower growing organisms are thus at an advantage in low nutrient environments.
- **maximum Chl:C** – the higher the value the more light energy can be captured. The downside is that with more Chl in the water column, less light is available (for all phototrophs), and having more Chl can make an organism more sensitive to excess light.
- **sensitivity to light** – the greater the sensitivity, the more damaging is high light, a situation made worse again if the organism becomes nutrient limited.
- **ascent rate** – the higher this value, the faster the organism can migrate. In a natural ecosystem, this motility can be dangerous as it increases the likelihood of encountering predators (not described here).

Model interface

The model interface is more complex than used in the previous Experiments; it now operates over a series of windows. You may need to alter the zoom magnification in each window so you can see all the components easily. Selecting '**fit**' from the zoom options will ensure the display is complete on your screen.

The entry window provides a brief introduction. Clicking the 'Configuration' button takes you to the actual simulator.

From the configuration window, not only do you have access to options to design your experiment, but there are also buttons to take you to 3 simulation display windows. You can switch windows during the simulation run. If you want to halt the simulations while you switch, use **Ctrl+space** to toggle between 'pause' and 'run'.

Each of the windows are described in detail below.

Configuration window

The screenshot shows the "Configuration" window with several sliders for parameters: Latitude north, Start month, Cloud, MLD (m), subM_NO3, subM_NH4, VED rate, and Sampling depth (m). A central box contains "BRIEF INSTRUCTIONS" and "PLEASE READ THE DOCUMENTATION BEFORE PROCEEDING". Below the instructions are two tables: "Abiotic configuration" and "Phytoplankton trait".

BRIEF INSTRUCTIONS

PLEASE READ THE DOCUMENTATION BEFORE PROCEEDING

Reset the simulation using Ctrl+R

Select the required latitude (degrees; 0 is equator, 80 is near the North Pole)

Select the required month (1 is January, 12 is December)

Set the level of cloudiness (0 is clear sky, 0.8 is 80% obscured)

Select the required mixed layer depth (m; MLD)

Set the sub-ergoline concentrations of the nutrients (gN m⁻³; these values also set the start concentrations in the mixed layer)

Set the sampling depth; if this is set at more than the value of MLD, then sampling is at the depth set by MLD

Set the vertical eddy diffusion rate (VED; m² d⁻¹); the higher this value the faster the system responds

Set the variables for the two phytoplankton species, species [1] and species [2]. These are for the following:-

- Initial biomass (initPhy; mgC m⁻³)
- Maximum growth rate (Um; d⁻¹)
- Maximum Chl:C content (ChlCm; g g⁻¹)
- Light level half suppressing photosynthesis through photo-damage (PinhK; umol m⁻² s⁻¹)
- Ascent rate; a negative value, below the red line, gives a descent (i.e., a sinking rate). Phytoplankton would have a positive value. (ASm; m d⁻¹)

Run the simulation using Ctrl+space; toggling this will pause and un-pause the simulation

You can alter 'Latitude', 'Month', 'Cloud' and physiological parameters during the simulation!

Abiotic configuration

Abiotic configuration	Setting	Unit
latitude	20.00	degrees north
start date	7.24	decimal month
Mixed Layer Depth (MLD)	30.00	m
Sampling depth	5.00	m
sub-MLD nitrate (NO ₃ ⁻)	70.00	mgN m ⁻³
sub-MLD ammonium (NH ₄ ⁺)	6.50	mgN m ⁻³
VED rate	50.00	m ² d ⁻¹

Phytoplankton trait

Phytoplankton trait	Species [1]	Species [2]	Unit	Comment
initial biomass	2.00	2.00	mgC m ⁻³	A value of 0 indicates that the species is not present
maximum growth rate	1.05	0.70	d ⁻¹	A doubling per day is given by a value of 0.7
maximum Chl:C	0.06	0.04	gChl gC ⁻¹	Higher values are better for low light
photodamage PFD	258.00	297.00	umol m ⁻² s ⁻¹	Higher values decrease sensitivity to high light
ascent rate	0.00	4.00	m d ⁻¹	Positive values support vertical migration to light and nutrients

This window contains a set of brief instructions.

Features that you can alter are described below. They are altered through use of the sliders; if the slider does not register your actions, reset the simulation (**Ctrl+R**) and try again. Note that you can alter 'Latitude', 'Month', 'Cloud' and physiological parameters during the simulation! Values set by the sliders are also tabulated. It may help to revisit **Fig.2**.

- **Latitude** (degrees N); this geolocates the simulation between 0° (equator) and 80°N (inside the Arctic circle).
- **Month**; this sets the start day of the simulation. Together with Latitude, this governs the amount of light and the day-night periodicity.
- **Cloud**; this allows you to further modify the amount of light that reaches the water surface.
- **Mixed layer depth (MLD; m)**; this can be altered between 10-50 m.
- **Sampling depth (m)**; typically during real water sampling, a volume of water for analysis is taken from only one depth (often just below the surface, 1m, or at 5m). Here, you can explore whether taking a sample at a specific depth does indeed give a good reflection of the biomass throughout the mixed layer. **Note:** If you try to set a sampling depth greater than the MLD value you have set, then the actual sampling depth will take the value of MLD.
- Initial and sub-mixed layer nitrate and ammonium (**subM_NO3, subM_NH4**; mgN m⁻³). These are the nutrients used by the phytoplankton. Phytoplankton exhibit a preference for ammonium; this source will be used first as provides for more efficient growth. This is because an organism using nitrate has to convert that N source into ammonium, and to do so it needs to use energy that it could otherwise use for growth. The relative usage of ammonium and nitrate is reported by an index called the *f*-ratio. The *f*-ratio has a value of 0 if only ammonium is being used, and 1 if only nitrate is used.
- **Mixed layer vertical eddy diffusion (VED) rate**; the calmer the mixed layer the slower this will be but here you may wish to alter it also just to slow down the simulation so you can better observe what is happening. VED can be altered between 10 and 50 m² d⁻¹. The exchange rate between the lowest part of the mixed layer and the sub-mixed layer is set at 5% of the mixed layer VED but it is also capped so it does not represent more than a total exchange rate of 0.03 d⁻¹.

Note that clicking above or below the current slider position will make the slider jump to exactly the next numbered position on the slider. This is useful for recreating conditions between tests.

Growth of the phytoplankton, as described here, is a function of light entering at the surface and passing down through the water column, and of nutrients that enter the bottom of the mixed water column and diffuse up through it. The availability of light depends on the location of the water column; here you can alter that with reference to the latitude and also the time of year.

Light has units of $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; this tells you how many photons (packages of light) land on each square meter per second. The value is described as a *Photon Flux Density*, or PFD. A value of PFD for a sunny summers day, with a clear sky, is around 2000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. This value is decreased rapidly if clouds obscure the sun. For reference, the value of PFD within a metre of a normal household electric lamp is around 100-200 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. The minimum amount needed to support growth rate of phytoplankton is around 10-20 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (i.e., 1% of the maximum surface value); see the inset for **Fig.3**.

There are two phytoplankton species described by the model; species [1] and species [2]. The features that you can modify for these are as follows:

- **Initial biomass (initPhy; mgC m⁻³)**; this describes the starting biomass for each species. If you do not want a species present, enter 0 for this species. Note that if you decide to only supply low concentrations of nutrient (low values of **subM_NO3, subM_NH4**) you should start the simulation with a smaller initial biomass, otherwise growth will become nutrient-limited very quickly.

- Maximum growth rate (**Um**; d^{-1}); this describes the maximum rate at which the phytoplankton can grow. A value of $0.693 d^{-1}$ describes a rate of growth that doubles the biomass each day; half this value enables a doubling of the biomass every 2 days, while using a value of 2x this value enables 2 doublings of the biomass per day. The actual growth rate is limited by the amount of light and nutrient available over the day.
- Maximum Chl:C content (**ChlCm**; $g g^{-1}$); this describes how much of the photosynthetic pigment chlorophyll the species can contain. The higher this value, the more light energy can be captured (**Fig.3**). The value of **ChlCm** sets the maximum pigment content as the grams of chlorophyll present per g of phytoplankton biomass. The actual value of Chl:C changes as the phytoplankton acclimate to the amount of light available (Chl:C decreases if there is sufficient light), while nutrient-limitation leads a decline in Chl:C.). Too much pigment can result in the capture of a damaging amounts of energy; that is more likely if growth is nutrient-limited. The collective pigment within the water column also shades light from the phytoplankton, decreasing light availability. Motile phytoplankton may migrate to more nutrient rich low-light conditions to balance their needs for C (from photosynthesis) and N.
- Light level that half suppresses photosynthesis through photo-damage (**PinhK**; $\mu mol photons m^{-2} s^{-1}$); too much light can bring in too much energy to the phytoplankton cell. If the cell cannot use this energy for growth then the energy causes damage to the cell structure, and specifically to the photosystems that perform photosynthesis. A low level of light (i.e., a low PFD, of around $50 \mu mol photons m^{-2} s^{-1}$) will not cause damage, but PFD values above 100 are increasingly likely to damage the photosystems. The value of **PinhK** sets the PFD value that causes sufficient damage to cut the expected rate of photosynthesis by 50%. The higher the value of **PinhK**, the more light the phytoplankton can withstand without damage being caused. Organisms that are sensitive to light tend to grow best lower in the water column; vertical migration (controlled in the model by the ascent rate, **ASm**) moves phytoplankton away from damaging light.
- Maximum ascent rate (**ASm**; $m d^{-1}$); this value controls the maximum rate at which the phytoplankton can migrate up or down in the water column. A value of zero (indicated by the red line on the slider) sets a neutral buoyancy, with no ascent or descent. Note, however, that vertical eddy diffusion (see Experiments 2– 5) will still move, still distribute, the phytoplankton within the water column. For phytoplankton, ascent is driven by nutrient sufficiency and hence that they are well equipped to exploit light (which is higher at the surface). Conversely, descent is driven by nutrient starvation and thence a surplus of C; the organisms migrate down away from the light towards more nutrients that are present at the ergocline. A similar migration is stimulated by photoinhibition; if the light is sufficiently high to cause damage, a motile phytoplankton can swim away from it rather than be killed by the high light. For phytoplankton, a positive value of **ASm** is expected, but here you can experiment with using a zero value or even a negative value.

Run the simulation using **Ctrl+space**; toggling this will pause and un-pause the simulation allowing you to switch between the results windows.

IMPORTANT: the other windows, detailed below, all show different data types but from the same simulation. Comparing between the plots, between windows of results, helps you understand what is happening.

Running the model

- Start off by resetting the simulation, by pressing **Ctrl+R**. Then make your selections using the sliders.
- **Start a simulation** by pressing **Ctrl+space**.
- You can **pause the simulation** at any time by pressing **Ctrl+space**; un-pause by repeating **Ctrl+space**.
- To **reset the simulation**, to start a new run, press **Ctrl+R**.

Overview window

This window contains a brief information panel. Press F9 to autoscale the plots during the simulation.

The following provides greater detail.

- **Light with depth;** the x-axis is depth (m), the y-axis is the light (as PFD, $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). As the simulation time changes (bottom right-hand corner of the display), the plot shows light changing. It is highest at the surface and at midday (when the decimal fraction of the simulation time is 0.5). As the biomass (of both phytoplankton species) grows, the attenuation of the light increases so that less light penetrates deeper into the water column.
- **Nutrients and biomass with depth;** the x-axis is depth (m), the y-axis is the amount of nutrient and also the N-biomass (mgN m^{-3}). The line types show the concentration of ammonium (NH_4) and nitrate (NO_3), and also for the two phytoplankton species. You will notice that ammonium is used first, and that nutrients are consumed from the surface waters faster. Nutrients also enter the water column from the bottom of the mixed layer (i.e., at the maximum depth shown on the x-axis).
- **Light with time;** the x-axis is time (d), the y-axis is the light (as PFD, $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). The plot shows how the light at the surface (PFD) and the average light within the mixed layer depth (avgE) change over time. The gradual changes in the peak PFD values reflect how the amount of sunlight changes as the time changes; if your start setting for month was between 22nd December and 21st June then this value will gradually increase as the year progresses to mid

summer, otherwise it will gradually decrease as the year progresses to mid winter. The difference between PFD and avgE will mirror changes in the 'Light with depth' plot.

- **Nutrients and biomass with time;** the x-axis is time (d), the y-axis is the amount of nutrient and also the N-biomass (mgN m^{-2}). The line types show the concentration of ammonium (NH_4) and nitrate (NO_3), and also for the two phytoplankton species. Note that these concentrations are the areal values; that is, they report the total amount of N for each of the categories (nutrient, biomass) beneath a 1 m^2 area at the surface down to the bottom of the mixed layer (see **Fig.2** to orientate yourself). From this plot you will see that ammonium is used by preference, and you will also see how the whole population of phytoplankton species 1 competes with species 2 in terms of the N-biomass.
- **C-fixation with time;** the x-axis is time (d), the y-axis is the rate of C-fixation (i.e., photosynthesis, $\text{mgC m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$). Note that these rates are the areal values; that is, they report the total amount of C fixed per day for each of the categories (species 1, species 2, total) beneath a 1 m^2 area at the surface down to the bottom of the mixed layer. From this plot you will see how the whole population of phytoplankton species 1 competes with species 2 in terms of the rate of C-fixation.
- **C-biomass with time;** the x-axis is time (d), the y-axis is the amount of C-biomass (mgC m^{-2}). Note that these are the areal values; that is, they report the total amount of C for each of the categories (species 1, species 2, total) beneath a 1 m^2 area at the surface down to the bottom of the mixed layer. From this plot you will see how the whole population of phytoplankton species 1 competes with species 2 in terms of the C-biomass.

Any relative differences between the N-biomass and C-biomass plots reflect changes in the nutrient status of the phytoplankton. As the phytoplankton exhaust the supply of nutrients (ammonium and then nitrate), they continue to photosynthesise, although at a decreasing rate. This results in the ratio of C to N (C:N) in their biomass increasing as they deposit surplus C in the form of starch or lipid rather than combining it with N to make protein and nucleic acids to support cell replication. You will see these events playing out in the *Physiology detail* window.

Physiology detail window

This window contains a brief information panel. Press F9 to autoscale the plots during the simulation.

The following provides greater detail. Some plots repeat detail from the Overview window. All plots are with depth (m); the x-axis runs from the surface to the maximum mixed layer depth.

Light and nutrients

- **Light**; the y-axis is the light (as PFD, $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). As the simulation time changes (bottom right-hand corner of the display), the plot shows light changing. It is highest at the surface and at midday (when the decimal fraction of the simulation time is 0.5). As the biomass grows, the attenuation of the light increases so that less light penetrates deep into the water column.
- **Nutrients**; the y-axis is the amount of nutrient (mgN m^{-3}). The line types show the concentration of ammonium (NH_4) and nitrate (NO_3). You will notice that ammonium is used first, and that nutrients are consumed from the surface waters faster. Nutrients also enter the system from the bottom of the mixed layer (i.e., at the maximum depth on the x-axis).

C-fixation and photoinhibition

- **C-fixation**; the y-axis is the C-specific rate of photosynthesis ($\text{C C}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$). This tells you, for species 1 and species 2, for every gram of C-biomass, how many grams of C are being added through C-fixation. This rate is not the same as the growth rate because some of the newly fixed C is respired to support biosynthesis. The use of nitrate, rather than ammonium, also affects growth as that nutrient is especially expensive to use. You will see that the value of C-fixation is lower at depth but, depending on the amount of surface light and sensitivity of the phytoplankton to photoinhibition, it may be optimal several metres below the surface. The values will vary as sunlight at the surface changes with day and night, with cloud cover and also with the developing total phytoplankton biomass as this attenuates (cuts out) light.
- **Photoinhibition**; the y-axis is the index of photoinhibition (1 indicates high levels of damage). This tells you, for species 1 and species 2, how damaging is the light at each depth. The values will vary as sunlight at the surface changes with day and night, and with total phytoplankton biomass as this attenuates (cuts out) light.

N:C and N-status

- **N:C**; the y-axis is the ratio of N-biomass to C-biomass (gN gC^{-1}), with values given for species 1 and species 2. Nutrient-replete (i.e., healthy) phytoplankton have ratios higher than 0.15. As the nutrient (ammonium and then nitrate) is exhausted, and the phytoplankton continue to fix C, the N:C decreases. As light for C-fixation enters at the surface, while nutrient (ammonium, nitrate) enters at the bottom of the mixed layer, you will see the surface N:C declining more rapidly than the N:C values at depth. Also, faster growing phytoplankton may be more sensitive to nutrient availability. The values of N:C will vary as sunlight at the surface changes with day and night, affecting the rate of photosynthesis, and also with the availability and supply of nutrients.
- **N-status**; the y-axis is an index for the phytoplankton N-status, with values given for species 1 and species 2. A value for N-status of 1 indicates satiation (aligning with a maximum N:C), while a value of 0 indicates extreme N-starvation (aligning with a minimum N:C, which is around 0.05 gN gC^{-1}). The N-status affects not only the growth rate but also the way that the phytoplankton can respond to light (too much or too little) and also, if appropriate, it affects vertical migration (see below).

Chl:C and C-status

- **Chl:C**; the y-axis is the ratio of chlorophyll to C-biomass (gChl gC^{-1}), with values given for species 1 and species 2. Phytoplankton acclimate to the availability of light by changing the amount of

pigment required to capture light energy. The main pigment is chlorophyll (Chl). If there is sufficient light, Chl:C will be low, but if there is insufficient light and assuming there is sufficient nutrient to support growth, Chl:C will increase (the organism becoming darker in colour) until Chl:C attains a maximum (which is set on the *Configuration* window using **ChlCm**). You will see that the values for Chl:C vary as light and nutrients change with depth; note that as the total population grows, it shades out light from penetrating deeper into the water column so phytoplankton living in deep waters are more likely to have a high Chl:C.

- **C-status**; the y-axis is an index for the phytoplankton C-status, with values given for species 1 and species 2. A value for C-status of 1 indicates a good status, while a value of 0 indicates extreme C-starvation. Optimal growth requires both the C-status and the N-status (see above) to be maximum. The values will vary as sunlight at the surface changes with day and night, affecting the rate of photosynthesis. The N-status will also have an effect because only organisms that have a high N-status will be able to synthesis metabolic systems that work well.

Growth and death

- **Growth rate**; the y-axis is the growth rate ignoring death (i.e., gross growth rate), with values given for species 1 and species 2. The values are as $\text{gC gC}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$, which is the same as d^{-1} . A value of 0.693 d^{-1} (on average over the whole day) equates to a doubling of the biomass every day. Compare these values to those for C-fixation (see above); these growth rate values are lower because of the losses through respiration. The values go negative at night because respiration continues in the absence of photosynthesis.
- **Growth – death**; the y-axis is the growth rate minus death (i.e., net growth rate), with values given for species 1 and species 2. The values are as $\text{gC gC}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$. Death occurs due to stress incurred by exposure to too much light near the surface (i.e., high photoinhibition) and also with insufficient nutrient (i.e., a low N-status).

Ascent and *f*-ratio

- **Ascent**; the y-axis is the ascent rate (m d^{-1}), with values given for species 1 and species 2. Positive values indicate a movement towards the surface; negative indicates movement down. The red dashed line indicates a status with neutral buoyancy. Assuming that **ASm** (set in the *Configuration* window) is not zero, the values will vary as sunlight at the surface changes with day and night, and also in response to photoinhibition and/or N-status.
- ***f*-ratio**; the y-axis is the *f*-ratio (no dimensions), with values given for species 1 and species 2. Phytoplankton exhibit a preference for ammonium; this resource will be used first. The relative usage of ammonium and nitrate is reported by the *f*-ratio. The *f*-ratio has a value of 0 if only ammonium is being used, and 1 if only nitrate is used. The *f*-ratio is expected to be lower at depth as the phytoplankton will exploit the ammonium by priority rather than nitrate diffusing up into the mixed layer.

Sampling window

This window contains a brief information panel. Press F9 to autoscale the plots during the simulation.

In the *Configuration* window, you selected a sampling depth. The value is shown here above the plots to remind you of the value being used.

The plots allow you to consider whether your selected sampling depth would have provided you with a fair representation of events throughout the water column. Samples taken at depth and analysed would provide you with information on abundances or concentrations expressed as a value per cubic metre (m^{-3}), or perhaps per litre. To determine the average value over the mixed layer requires you to know the mixed layer depth; you set the value of the MLD for the simulations in the *Configurations* window.

Here the data for the sampling depth and the average over the mixed layer have been presented using the same units so you can readily compare them. If the sampling at your chosen depth gave a good representation of events over the whole water column, these values would be equal.

There are two types of plot provided for each of the two phytoplankton species (Phyto[1], and Phyto[2]). It is instructive to watch the simulation to observe the plots being generated in real time; use F9 as required to autoscale the plots during the simulation.

- **Biomass with time;** here, if the sampling was representative then the average values (Avg_Phyto) and the sample taken at the sampling depth (SD) would be the same and the plot lines would overlay each other.
- **SD vs average;** in these x,y scatter plots, the value at the sample depth is shown against the average value. If the sampling was representative then the plot would be linear and the numeric extent of the x-axis and y-axis would be the same. If the plot was linear but the axes not equal, then a relationship could still be used; the problem is if the plot shows a more complex curve (as seen in the screen-shot example shown above, especially for species 2).

Things to explore

Note that the sliders will stay in their position between simulations; you can thus experiment altering one factor at a time, which is the best way to conduct the initial stages of any scientific experiment.

This is a complex model with very many permutations to explore. After an initial exploration of the interface to better understand how to use the model, it would be logical to design specific experiments with hypotheses. You may also wish to first consider operating the model with just one species (set the initial biomass of the other species at zero). You may also wish to design a series of investigations following the 'Things to explore' sections of earlier Experiments.

There are two primary routes to exploring the system:

- i) set the abiotic system and try different phytoplankton configurations and competitions
- ii) set the phytoplankton configuration(s) and try different abiotic systems

To proceed, consider the following -

- Explore different permutations of latitude and date (i.e. **Latitude, Month**), cloudiness (**Cloud**), mixed layer depth (**MLD**) and nutrient loading (**subM_NO3, subM_NH4**)
- Configure the two species of phytoplankton in contrasting ways. For example:

Parameter Configuration	Species 1	Species 2
Um	1.5	0.7
ChlCm	0.06	0.03
PinhK	400	200
ASm	0	4

In all instances try and explain why you are observing the changes in the plots. Try to summarize what you observe. Use expertise you have gained from operating the earlier Experiments.

In all instances, try and explain or justify what you are seeing. Also criticize the results set against the **Caveats** given below.

Caveats

Recall that simulations are always simplifications of reality. It is important to consider how your understanding of real events may be affected by such simplifications. The same, incidentally, applies to all studies of natural systems, and not just to simulations.

There is no change in MLD during the simulation. Here, the simulation duration is 50d. It is extremely unlikely that the MLD will remain unchanged over this period, especially over winter. You can, however, adjust VED.

The main caveat here is that no predators are described; predators are introduced to the system in Experiment 7.

Predators have several actions in such an ecosystem:

1. they control (*modulate*) the success of their prey – this may differ depending on the absolute (e.g., mgC m⁻³ biomass of each species) and relative (i.e., ratio of abundance of the prey species to total prey) concentration of the prey.

2. The nutritional value of those prey affects both selectivity for each prey (some may become toxic as well as being of lower nutritional value when nutrient-stressed) and also the transfer of prey-biomass to predator-biomass. Nutrient-stressed prey may, for example, be avoided, or on the contrary consumed rapidly but with little benefit to increasing the predator biomass.
3. Predator growth, through consumption of the phytoplankton prey, results in the release (technically termed as a 'regeneration') of nutrients.

It will be apparent from a combination of these interactions that there is scope for the development of a bloom of phytoplankton that, because of its poor nutritional value, fails to support a growth of an effective predator population. The simulation here, with no predator description, could be viewed as an extreme example, where the phytoplankton are never palatable.

There is only one limiting nutrient described here, dissolved inorganic N. In reality other nutrients are likely to be potentially limiting. These include phosphorous (P), iron (Fe), vitamins, and especially for a certain group of important phytoplankton (the diatoms), silicon (Si).

There is an additional interaction that can be important in reality that is not included. That is an interaction between phytoplankton species. Such interactions are caused by the release of organic chemicals made by the organisms called **allelopaths**. These chemicals can damage the growth of competitor organisms. The interaction is a function of biomass abundance; the more cells there are of an allelopathic species the more allelopaths are released and the greater is the impact on competitors.

Experiment 7 Nutrient-Light-limited growth of a phytoplankton-zooplankton community in the water column

You should have completed Experiments 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 before proceeding.

For this experiment you will use a simulation model that describes organism (phytoplankton) growth within the mixed layer. Like Experiments 4 and 5, here the light is described according to the selected latitude and month of the year. Like Experiment 6, there are 2 phytoplankton species which you can configure and which grow in competition. The advance is the inclusion of a zooplankton predator.

The simulation model for this experiment is named **1D_Exp7.sip**. This operates within a free (no-cost) application **Powersim Cockpit** that needs to be installed on your Windows PC. Please check the **Quick Start** section at the start of this document for details.

You cannot 'break' the model; in the unlikely event that something does go wrong, just reload the simulation file.

Expected duration of this experiment: 60+ min.

Use the print-screen option to record your simulation outputs; you can then paste the screen copy into another application.

WARNING – this experiment represents a significant increase in complexity over the previous experiments. It is easy to become disorientated when confronted with so many permutations to explore.

Remember, that a simulation, even a very complex one, is much simpler than the real world. As with working in the real world, be methodical in how you approach the task. Do not feel that you need to alter everything; if in doubt set sliders to a mid position while you explore just a few variables.

This activity builds on those in Experiment 6 but now introduces a zooplankton that can graze selectively on the two phytoplankton. The model supporting this experiment has many more options than those available in the previous Experiments. Indeed, like Experiment 6, the permutations available would make this activity one that is open-ended and well suited to student project work extending over many hours.

Before proceeding, it is worth considering the functionality of the zooplankton.

Zooplankton functionality

Zooplankton are consumers of phytoplankton, and also of bacteria, mixoplankton and of other zooplankton. Zooplankton come in two basic forms:

- 1) protist zooplankton – single celled microscopic organisms which typically grow rapidly by simple cell division, are efficient at converting prey biomass into their own biomass, and also display high levels of prey selectivity.
- 2) metazoan zooplankton – multi-cellular organisms with sizes ranging from microscopic to m dimensions, typically grow rather slowly, are less efficient and, other than for selection by prey

size, may display lower levels of prey selectivity. Importantly, typically these organisms have complex life histories with eggs, various juvenile stages and adult females and males.

All zooplankton have to encounter, capture and then consume prey. They digest the prey, retaining a portion while voiding the remainder; the efficiency of this process is recorded as the 'assimilation efficiency', **AE**.

AE varies typically from very inefficient (ca. $AE=0.1$, 10% assimilated) to highly efficient (ca. $AE=0.9$, 90% assimilated). Efficiency varies depending on:

- the type of zooplankton (those with a gut are typically less efficient because the gut requires undigested material in it for the peristaltic action to work),
- the amount of prey being ingested (when prey is readily available, it tends to be handled with a lower efficiency),
- the type of prey (some organisms are inherently more easily digested)
- nutrient status of the prey (nutrient-deplete prey are of lower food quality).

After the loss of potential food value with AE, another 30% or so is lost through the metabolic processing of what is brought into the organism. Only one type of consumer avoids that 30% cost, and those are the **mixoplankton** which can use photosynthesis to immediately recover nutrients that would otherwise be lost. A zooplankton, in contrast, will have lost the C, N and P (and other elements) as dissolved compounds during that processing.

Even when they are not feeding, zooplankton will be respiring, consuming energy to hunt and maintain their biochemical operations. Some can cannibalise to enable the individual to survive when other prey are absent.

As you will appreciate, it is complicated, so for this simulation we will make some simplifications. The first of those is that we assume that the zooplankton is a protist so we can ignore life-cycle changes. Nonetheless, the protist zooplankton can be configured in several ways, as will be described below.

Model interface

The model interface is more complex than used in the earlier Experiments; like Experiment 6, it now operates over a series of windows. You may need to alter the zoom magnification in each window so you can see all the components easily. Selecting '**fit**' from the zoom options will ensure the display is complete on your screen.

The entry window provides a brief introduction. Clicking the 'Configuration' button takes you to the actual simulator.

From the configuration window, not only do you have access to options to design your experiment, but also there are buttons to take you to 3 simulation display windows. You can switch windows during the simulation run. If you want to halt the simulations while you switch, use **Ctrl+space** to toggle between pause and run.

Each of the windows are described in detail below.

Configuration window

Configuration

Latitude north (0 to 80), **Start month** (1 to 12), **Cloud** (0.0 to 0.8), **MLD (m)** (0 to 50)

subM_NO3 (0 to 280), **subM_NH4** (0 to 70), **VED rate** (0 to 50), **Sampling depth (m)** (0 to 9)

Abiotic configuration

Abiotic configuration	Setting	Unit
latitude	40.00	degrees north
start date	7.24	decimal month
Mixed Layer Depth (MLD)	40.00	m
Sampling depth	10.00	m
sub-MLD nitrate (NO3-)	66.50	mgN m-3
sub-MLD ammonium (NH4+)	8.00	mgN m-3
VED rate	25.00	m2 d-1

BRIEF INSTRUCTIONS

PLEASE READ THE DOCUMENTATION BEFORE PROCEEDING

Reset the simulation using Ctrl+R

Select the required latitude (degrees; 0 is equator, 80 is near the North Pole)

Select the required month (1 is January, 12 is December)

Set the level of cloudiness (0 is clear sky, 0.8 is 80% obscured)

Select the required mixed layer depth (m; MLD)

Set the sub-argline concentrations of the nutrients (gN m⁻³); these values also set the start concentrations in the mixed layer

Set the sampling depth; if this is set at more than the value of MLD, then sampling is at the depth set by MLD

Set the vertical eddy diffusion rate (VED; m² d⁻¹); the higher this value the faster the system responds

Set the variables for the two phytoplankton species, species [1] and species [2]. These are for the following:-

- Initial biomass (initPhy; mgC m⁻³)
- Maximum growth rate (ZUm; d⁻¹)
- Maximum Chl:C content (ChlCm; g p⁻¹)
- Light level half suppressing photosynthesis through photodamage (PinhK; umol m⁻² s⁻¹)
- Ascent rate when lacking C (ASm; m d⁻¹)

Set the variables for the zooplankton. These are for the following:-

- Initial biomass (initZoo; mgC m⁻³)
- Maximum growth rate (ZUm; d⁻¹)
- Prey preference parameters for phytoplankton species [1] and [2] and for cannibalism (CRI_p, CRI_can [(Prey-C)/(Pred-C)] d/(mg prey biomass m³))
- Ascent rate when starving (ASm_zoo; m d⁻¹)

Run the simulation using Ctrl+space; toggling this will pause and un-pause the simulation

You can alter 'Latitude', 'Month', 'Cloud' and physiological parameters during the simulation!!

Phytoplankton trait

Phytoplankton trait	Species [1]	Species [2]	Unit	Comment
initial biomass	4.00	4.00	mgC m-3	A value of 0 indicates that the species is not present
maximum growth rate	1.05	0.70	d-1	A doubling per day is given by a value of 0.7
maximum Chl:C	0.06	0.04	gChl gC-1	Higher values are better for low light
photodamage PFD	258.00	297.00	umol m-2 s-1	Higher values decrease sensitivity to high light
ascent rate	0.00	4.00	m d-1	Positive values support vertical migration to light and nutrients

Zooplankton trait

Zooplankton trait	Setting	Unit
initial biomass	2.00	mgC m-3
preference for Phy[1]	6.00e-3	see text
preference for Phy[2]	3.22e-3	see text
preference for cannibalism	0.00	see text

This window contains a set of brief instructions.

Features that you can alter are described below. They are altered through use of the sliders; if the slider does not register your actions, reset the simulation (**Ctrl+R**) and try again. Note that you can alter 'Latitude', 'Month', 'Cloud' and physiological parameters during the simulation! Values set by the sliders are also tabulated. It may help to revisit **Fig.2**.

- **Latitude** (degrees N); this geolocates the simulation between 0° (equator) and 80°N (inside the Arctic circle).
- **Month**; this sets the start day of the simulation. Together with Latitude, this governs the amount of light and the day-night periodicity.

- **Cloud**; this allows you to further modify the amount of light that reaches the water surface.
- Mixed layer depth (**MLD**; m); this can be altered between 10-50 m.
- **Sampling depth** (m); typically during real water sampling, a volume of water for analysis is taken from only one depth (often just below the surface, 1m, or at 5m). Here, you can explore whether taking a sample at a specific depth does indeed give a good reflection of the biomass throughout the mixed layer. **Note:** If you try to set a sampling depth greater than the MLD value you have set, then the actual sampling depth will take the value of MLD.
- Initial and sub-mixed layer nitrate and ammonium (**subM_NO3**, **subM_NH4**; mgN m⁻³). These are the nutrients used by the phytoplankton. Phytoplankton exhibit a preference for ammonium; this source will be used first as provides for more efficient growth. This is because an organism using nitrate has to convert that N source into ammonium, and to do so it needs to use energy that it could otherwise use for growth. The relative usage of ammonium and nitrate is reported by an index called the *f*-ratio. The *f*-ratio has a value of 0 if only ammonium is being used, and 1 if only nitrate is used. Note also that zooplankton release ammonium as a waste product!
- Mixed layer vertical eddy diffusion (**VED**) rate; the calmer the mixed layer the slower this will be but here you may wish to alter it also just to slow down the simulation so you can better observe what is happening. VED can be altered between 10 and 50 m² d⁻¹. The exchange rate between the lowest part of the mixed layer and the sub-mixed layer is set at 5% of the mixed layer VED but it is also capped so it does not represent more than a total exchange rate of 0.03 d⁻¹.

Note that clicking above or below the current slider position will make the slider jump to exactly the next numbered position on the slider. This is useful for recreating conditions between tests.

Growth of the phytoplankton, as described here, is a function of light entering at the surface and passing down through the water column, and of nutrients that enter the bottom of the mixed water column and diffuse up through it. The availability of light depends on the location of the water column; here you can alter that with reference to the latitude and also the time of year.

Light has units of $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$; this tells you how many photons (packages of light) land on each square meter per second. The value is described as a *Photon Flux Density*, or PFD. A value of PFD for a sunny summers day, with a clear sky, is around 2000 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. This value is decreased rapidly if clouds obscure the sun. For reference, the value of PFD within a metre of a normal household electric lamp is around 100-200 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. The minimum amount needed to support growth of phytoplankton is around 10-20 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ (i.e., 1% of the maximum surface value; See the inset for **Fig.3**).

There are two phytoplankton species described by the model; species [1] and species [2]. The features that you can modify for these are as follows:

- Initial biomass (**initPhy**; mgC m⁻³); this describes the starting biomass for each species. If you do not want a species present, enter 0 for this value. Note that if you decide to only supply low concentrations of nutrient (low values of **subM_NO3**, **subM_NH4**) you should start the simulation with a smaller initial biomass, otherwise growth will become nutrient-limited very quickly.
- Maximum growth rate (**Um**; d⁻¹); this describes the maximum rate at which the phytoplankton can grow. A value of 0.693 d⁻¹ describes a rate of growth that doubles the biomass each day; half this value enables a doubling of the biomass every 2 days, while using a value of 2x this value enables 2 doublings of the biomass per day. The actual growth rate is limited by the amount of light and nutrient available.

- Maximum Chl:C content (**ChlCm**; g g^{-1}); this describes how much of the photosynthetic pigment chlorophyll the species can contain. The higher this value, the more light energy can be captured. However, too much pigment can capture damaging amounts of energy. The collective pigment within the water column also shades light from the phytoplankton, decreasing light availability. The value of **ChlCm** sets the maximum pigment content as the grams of chlorophyll present per g of phytoplankton biomass. The actual value of Chl:C changes as the phytoplankton acclimate to the amount of light available (Chl:C decreases if there is sufficient light), while nutrient-limitation leads a decline in Chl:C.
- Light level that half suppresses photosynthesis through photo-damage (**PinhK**; $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$); too much light can bring in too much energy to the phytoplankton cell. If the cell cannot use this energy for growth then the energy causes damage to the cell structure, and specifically to the photosystems that perform photosynthesis. A low light level (i.e., a low PFD, of around $50 \mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) will not cause damage, but PFD values above 100 are increasingly likely to damage the photosystems. The value of **PinhK** sets the PFD value that causes sufficient damage to cut the expected rate of photosynthesis by 50%. The higher the value of **PinhK**, the more light the phytoplankton can withstand without damage being caused. Organisms that are sensitive to light tend to grow best lower in the water column; vertical migration (controlled in the model by the ascent rate, **ASm**) moves phytoplankton away from damaging light.
- Maximum ascent rate (**ASm**; m d^{-1}); this value controls the maximum rate at which the phytoplankton can migrate up or down in the water column. A value of zero sets a neutral buoyancy. Note, that vertical eddy diffusion (see Experiments 2– 5) will contribute to moving, distributing, the phytoplankton within the water column. For phytoplankton, ascent is driven by nutrient sufficiency and hence that they are well equipped to exploit light (which is higher at the surface). Conversely, descent is driven by nutrient starvation and thence a surplus of C; the organisms migrate down away from the light towards more nutrients that are present at the ergocline. A similar migration is stimulated by photoinhibition; if the light is sufficiently high to cause damage, a motile phytoplankton can swim away from it rather than be killed by the high light.

For simplicity, the protist zooplankton can be configured through only a few options.

- Initial biomass (**initZoo**; mgC m^{-3}); this describes the starting biomass for the zooplankton. The larger the starting biomass the more quickly the phytoplankton growth will become controlled by predatory activity. This interaction is termed **match-mismatch**. Mismatch is more likely to occur in shallow well-lit (i.e. summer) high nutrient water columns.
- Maximum growth rate (**ZUm**; d^{-1}); this describes the maximum rate at which the zooplankton can grow. A value of 0.693 d^{-1} describes a rate of growth that doubles the biomass each day; half this value enables a doubling of the biomass every 2 days. The grazing rate is much faster than the growth rate, because of the losses in inefficiency during assimilation and metabolic interconversions.
- Preference for each prey (**CRi_p**; $([\text{prey-C}]/[\text{pred-C}]/\text{d})/(\text{mg prey biomass}/\text{m}^3)$); these values describe prey capture rates taking into account all factors affecting prey encounter, and the success of capture. This capture rate is the maximum performed by a starved zooplankton. As satiation develops, the actual capture rate declines; a zooplankton that is replete will not feed.
- Cannibalism (**Cri_can**; $([\text{prey-C}]/[\text{pred-C}]/\text{d})/(\text{mg prey biomass}/\text{m}^3)$); this value controls if cannibalism may occur. Normally, cannibalism would only be significant in the absence of other (non-self) prey sources.

- Maximum ascent rate (**ASm_zoo**; m d^{-1}); this value controls the maximum rate at which the zooplankton can migrate up or down in the water column. A value of zero (indicated by the red line on the slider) sets a neutral buoyancy, with no ascent or descent. Note, however, that vertical eddy diffusion (see Experiments 2– 5) will still move, distribute, the zooplankton within the water column. For zooplankton, ascent is driven by starvation; if there is sufficient food at depth, out of the light, away from predators that hunt by sight, they will stay deep.

Run the simulation using **Ctrl+space**; toggling this will pause and un-pause the simulation allowing you to switch between the results windows.

IMPORTANT: the other windows, detailed below, all show different data types but from the same simulation. Comparing between the plots, between windows of results, helps you understand what is happening.

Running the model

- Start off by resetting the simulation, by pressing **Ctrl+R**. Then make your selections using the sliders.
- **Start a simulation** by pressing **Ctrl+space**.
- You can **pause the simulation** at any time by pressing **Ctrl+space**; un-pause by repeating **Ctrl+space**.
- To **reset the simulation**, to start a new run, press **Ctrl+R**.

Overview window

This window contains a brief information panel. Press F9 to autoscale the plots during the simulation.

The following provides greater detail.

- Light with depth;** the x-axis is depth (m), the y-axis is the light (as PFD, $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). As the simulation time changes (bottom right-hand corner of the display), the plot shows light changing. It is highest at the surface and at midday (when the decimal fraction of the simulation time is 0.5). As the biomass grows, the attenuation of the light increases so that less light penetrates deeper into the water column.
- Nutrients and biomass with depth;** the x-axis is depth (m), the y-axis is the amount of nutrient and also the N-biomass (mgN m^{-3}). The line types show the concentration of ammonium (NH_4) and nitrate (NO_3), for the two phytoplankton species, and for the zooplankton. You will notice that ammonium is used first, and that nutrients are consumed from the surface waters faster. Ammonium is the form of N released by the zooplankton; this becomes most apparent when zooplankton are more dominant than the phytoplankton. Nutrients also enter the system from the bottom of the mixed layer (i.e., at the maximum depth on the x-axis).
- Light with time;** the x-axis is time (d), the y-axis is the light (as PFD, $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$). The plot shows how the light at the surface (PFD) and the average light within the mixed layer depth (avgE) change over time. The gradual changes in the peak PFD values reflect how the amount of sunlight changes as the time changes; if your start setting for month was between 22nd December and 21st June then this value will gradually increase as the year progresses to mid summer, otherwise it will gradually decrease as the year progresses to mid winter. The difference between PFD and avgE will mirror changes in the 'Light with depth' plot.
- Nutrients and biomass with time;** the x-axis is time (d), the y-axis is the amount of nutrient and also the N-biomass (mgN m^{-2}). The line types show the concentration of ammonium (NH_4) and

nitrate (NO_3), for the two phytoplankton species and for zooplankton. Note that these concentrations are the areal values; that is, they report the total amount of N for each of the categories (nutrient, biomass) beneath a 1 m^2 area at the surface down to the bottom of the mixed layer. From this plot you will see that ammonium is used by preference, and you will see how the whole population of phytoplankton species 1 competes with species 2 in terms of the N-biomass, set against the activities of the zooplankton.

- **C-fixation with time;** the x-axis is time (d), the y-axis is the rate of C-fixation (i.e., photosynthesis, $\text{mgC m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$). Note that these rates are the areal values; that is, they report the total amount of C fixed per day for each of the categories (phytoplankton species 1, species 2, total) beneath a 1 m^2 area at the surface down to the bottom of the mixed layer. From this plot you will see how the whole population of phytoplankton species 1 competes with species 2 in terms of the rate of C-fixation.
- **C-biomass with time;** the x-axis is time (d), the y-axis is the amount of C-biomass (mgC m^{-2}). Note that these are the areal values; that is, they report the total amount of C for each of the categories (phytoplankton species 1, species 2, total, and also the zooplankton) beneath a 1 m^2 area at the surface down to the bottom of the mixed layer. From this plot you will see how the whole population of phytoplankton species 1 competes with species 2 in terms of the C-biomass, set against the activities of the zooplankton.

Any relative differences between the N-biomass and C-biomass plots reflect changes in the nutrient status of the phytoplankton. As the phytoplankton exhaust the supply of nutrients (ammonium, nitrate), they continue to photosynthesise, although at a decreasing rate. This results in the ratio of C to N (C:N) in their biomass increasing as they deposit surplus C in the form of starch or lipid rather than combining it with N to make protein and nucleic acids to support cell replication. You will see these events playing out in the *Physiology detail* window. The C:N of the zooplankton is constant.

Physiology detail window

This window contains a brief information panel. Press F9 to autoscale the depth plots during the simulation.

The following provides greater detail. All plots are with depth (m); the x-axis runs from the surface to the maximum mixed layer depth.

To provide a ready reference with the 'Overview' window, this plot is reproduced:

- **Nutrients and biomass with time;** the x-axis is time (d), the y-axis is the amount of nutrient and also the N-biomass (mgN m^{-2}). The line types show the concentration of ammonium (NH_4) and nitrate (NO_3), for the two phytoplankton species and for zooplankton. Note that these concentrations are the areal values; that is, they report the total amount of N for each of the categories (nutrient, biomass) beneath a 1 m^2 area at the surface down to the bottom of the mixed layer. From this plot you will see that ammonium is used by preference, and you will see how the whole population of phytoplankton species 1 competes with species 2 in terms of the N-biomass, set against the activities of the zooplankton.

Light and nutrients

- **Light;** the y-axis is the light (as PFD, $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$). As the simulation time changes (bottom right-hand corner of the display), the plot shows light changing. It is highest at the surface and at midday (when the decimal fraction of the simulation time is 0.5). As the phytoplankton biomass grows, the attenuation of the light increases so that less light penetrates deep into the water column. As it is consumed by the zooplankton, the attenuation decreases.
- **Nutrients and biomass;** the y-axis is the amount of nutrient (mgN m^{-3}). The line types show the concentration of ammonium (NH_4) and nitrate (NO_3). You will notice that ammonium is used first, and that nutrients are consumed from the surface waters faster. Nutrients also enter the system from the bottom of the mixed layer (i.e., at the maximum depth on the x-axis), and ammonium is released by the zooplankton. Also shown are the N-biomass values for the two species of phytoplankton and of the zooplankton.

C-fixation and photoinhibition

- **C-fixation;** the y-axis is the C-specific rate of photosynthesis ($\text{C C}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$). This tells you, for phytoplankton species 1 and species 2, for every gram of C-biomass, how many grams of C are being added through C-fixation. This rate is not the same as the growth rate because some of the newly fixed C is respired to support biosynthesis. The use of nitrate, rather than ammonium, as the nutrient is especially expensive. You will see that the value is lower at depth but, depending on the amount of surface light and sensitivity of the phytoplankton to photoinhibition, it may be optimal several metres below the surface. The values will vary as sunlight at the surface changes with day and night.
- **Photoinhibition;** the y-axis is the index of photoinhibition (1 indicates high levels of damage). This tells you, for phytoplankton species 1 and species 2, how damaging is the light at each depth. The values will vary as sunlight at the surface changes with day and night.

N:C and N-status

- **N:C;** the y-axis is the ratio of N-biomass to C-biomass (gN gC^{-1}), with values given for phytoplankton species 1 and species 2. Nutrient-replete (healthy) phytoplankton have ratios higher than 0.15. As the nutrient (ammonium and then nitrate) is exhausted, and the phytoplankton continue to fix C, the N:C decreases. Because light for C-fixation enters at the surface, while nutrient (ammonium, nitrate) enters at the bottom of the mixed layer, you will see the surface N:C declining more than the values at depth. Also, faster growing phytoplankton may be more sensitive to nutrient availability. The values will vary as sunlight at the surface changes

with day and night, affecting the rate of photosynthesis, and also with the availability and supply of nutrients. Phytoplankton with a low N:C are of lower food value for the zooplankton.

- **N-status**; the y-axis is an index for the phytoplankton N-status, with values given for species 1 and species 2. A value of 1 indicates satiation (aligning with a maximum N:C), while a value of 0 indicates extreme N-starvation (aligning with a minimum N:C, which is around 0.05 gN gC⁻¹). The N-status affects not only the growth rate but also the way that the phytoplankton can respond to light (too much or too little), and also if appropriate it affects vertical migration (see below). Phytoplankton with a poor N-status are of lower food value for the zooplankton.

Chl:C and C-status

- **Chl:C**; the y-axis is the ratio of chlorophyll to C-biomass (gChl gC⁻¹), with values given for species 1 and species 2. Phytoplankton acclimate to the availability of light by changing the amount of pigment required to capture light energy. The main pigment is chlorophyll (Chl). If there is sufficient light, Chl:C will be low, but if there is insufficient light and assuming there is sufficient nutrient to support growth, Chl:C will increase (the organisms becoming darker in colour) until Chl:C attains a maximum (which is set on the *Configuration* window using **ChlCm**). You will see Chl:C vary as light and nutrients change with depth; note that as the total population grows, it shades out light from penetrating deep into the water column.
- **C-status**; the y-axis is an index for the phytoplankton C-status, with values given for species 1 and species 2. A value of 1 indicates a good status, while a value of 0 indicates extreme C-starvation. Optimal growth requires both the C-status and the N-status (see above) to be maximum. The values will vary as sunlight at the surface changes with day and night, affecting the rate of photosynthesis. The N-status will also have an effect because only cells that have a high N-status will be able to synthesis photosystems that work well.

Ingestion and satiation

- **Ingestion rate**; the y-axis is the C-specific ingestion rates for each of the phytoplankton species, and also for cannibalism into the zooplankton. Note that these values will, given sufficient prey abundance, be higher than the maximum growth rate set by **ZUm**. The difference is accounted for by inefficiencies in assimilation and biomass synthesis.
- **Satiation**; the y-axis is an index of zooplankton satiation. A value of 1 indicates full satiation, while 0 indicates starvation. If the value of **ASm_zoo** is not zero, then the rate of ascent for zooplankton will correlate with this satiation status.

Ascent and f-ratio

- **Ascent**; the y-axis is the ascent rate (m d⁻¹), with values given for phytoplankton species 1 and species 2, and also for the zooplankton. Positive values indicate a movement towards the surface; negative indicates movement down. The red dashed line indicates a status with neutral buoyancy. Assuming that **ASm** (set in the *Configuration* window) is not zero, the values for phytoplankton (AS_Phy) will vary as sunlight at the surface changes with day and night, and also in response to photoinhibition and/or N-status. The values for zooplankton (AS_Zoo) vary with satiation.
- **f-ratio**; the y-axis is the f-ratio (no dimensions), with values given for phytoplankton species 1 and species 2. Phytoplankton exhibit a preference for ammonium; this source will be used first. The relative usage of ammonium and nitrate is reported by the f-ratio. The f-ratio has a value of 0 if only ammonium is being used, and 1 if only nitrate is used. The f-ratio is lower at depth as

the phytoplankton will exploit the ammonium diffusing up into the mixed layer and also that released by the zooplankton (**Fig.1**).

Growth and death

- **Growth rate**; the y-axis is the growth rate ignoring death (i.e., gross growth rate), with values given for phytoplankton species 1 and species 2, and also for zooplankton. The values are as $\text{gC gC}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$. A value of 0.693 d^{-1} (on average, over the whole day) equates to a doubling of the biomass every day. Compared with rates for C-fixation and ingestion (see above), these growth rate values are lower because of the losses through respiration. The values go negative at night for phytoplankton, and negative for zooplankton if their ingestion rates are too low to compensate for their needs.
- **Growth – death**; the y-axis is the growth rate minus death (i.e., net growth rate), with values given for phytoplankton species 1 and species 2, and for zooplankton. The values are as $\text{gC gC}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$. Death occurs here due to stress incurred by exposure to too much light near the surface (i.e., high photoinhibition) and also with insufficient nutrient (i.e., a low N-status), for starvation for zooplankton.

Sampling window

This window contains a brief information panel. Press F9 to autoscale the plots during the simulation.

In the *Configuration* window, you selected a sampling depth. The value is shown here above the plots to remind you of the value being used.

The plots allow you to consider whether your selected sampling depth would have provided you with a fair representation of events throughout the water column. Samples taken at depth and analysed would provide you with information on abundances or concentrations expressed as a value per cubic metre (m^{-3}), or perhaps per litre. To determine the average value over the mixed layer requires you to know the mixed layer depth; you set this value for the simulations in the *Configurations* window.

Here the data for the sampling depth and the average over the mixed layer have been presented using the same units. If the sampling at your chosen depth gave a good representation of events over the whole water column, these values would be equal.

There are two types of plot for each of the two species (Phyto[1], and Phyto[2]) and also for the zooplankton. It is instructive to watch the simulation to observe the plots being generated in real time; use F9 as required to autoscale the plots.

- **Biomass with time**; here, if the sampling was representative then the average values (Avg_Phyto or Avg_Zoo) and the sample taken at the sampling depth (SD) would be the same.
- **SD vs average**; in these x,y scatter plots, the value at the sample depth is shown against the average value. If the sampling was representative then the plot would be linear and the numeric extent of the x-axis and y-axis would be the same. If the plot was linear but the axes not equal, then a relationship could still be used; the problem is if the plot shows a more complex curve (as seen in the screen-shot example shown above, especially for species 2).

Things to explore

Note that the sliders will stay in their position between simulations; you can thus experiment altering one factor at a time, which is the best way to conduct the initial stages of any scientific experiment.

This is a complex model with very many permutations to explore. After an initial exploration of the interface to better understand how to use the model, it would be logical to design specific experiments with hypotheses. You may also wish to first consider operating the model with just one phytoplankton species (set the initial biomass of the other at zero) to observe the interactions with the zooplankton consuming just a single prey item; remember to set **CRi_can** to zero otherwise the zooplankton will retain the opportunity to consume its own kind.

In all instances try and explain why you are observing the changes in the plots. Try to summarize what you observe. Use expertise you have gained from operating the earlier experiments.

Also criticize the results set against the **Caveats** given later in this section.

There are two primary routes to exploring the system:

- 1) set the abiotic system and try different phytoplankton configurations and competitions, and different zooplankton configurations
- 2) set the phytoplankton and zooplankton configuration(s) and try different abiotic systems

In pursuing these options, you could consider the following -

- Explore different permutations of latitude and date (i.e. **Latitude**, **Month**), cloudiness (**Cloud**), mixed layer depth (**MLD**) and nutrient loading (**subM_NO3**, **subM_NH4**)
- Configure the phytoplankton in contrasting ways. For example:

Configuration	Species 1	Species 2
Um	1.5	0.7
ChlCm	0.06	0.03
PinhK	400	200
ASm	0	4

- Configure the zooplankton in different ways, specifically with respect to the values of CRi which control the predation preferences. High values will support higher preferences, assuming the same biomass levels. Note that a high preference for a prey item that is only present at low biomass abundance will not prevent consumption of a lesser preferred prey item if that is present at a high abundance – any predator will modify its behaviour when it is starving.

Caveats

Recall that simulations are always simplifications of reality. It is important to consider how your understanding of real events may be affected by such simplifications. The same, incidentally, applies to all studies of natural systems, and not just to simulations.

There is no change in MLD during the simulation. Here, the simulation duration is 50d. It is unlikely that the MLD will remain unchanged over this period, especially over winter. You can, however, adjust VED.

It is unlikely that a nutrient addition would be made in water conditions like this. It is more likely that such an addition would occur near land where water current (including tidal flows) would add to the turbulence.

The main caveats, despite the apparent complexity of the description as set against a real plankton community ecosystem, are related to the description remaining very simple. Thus, in reality there would be:

- additional nutrient types (e.g., P, Fe, Si)
- more types of producers of different physiologies (different motilities, different nutrient needs) and also other interactions, related to allelopathy, for example
- more consumers (different protist and metazoan zooplankton, the latter including life stage descriptions)
- mixoplankton (which combine production and consumption in the one organism)
- bacteria to recycle the nutrients in the voided material
- viruses to especially control the growth of the more successful microbes

Size is not explicitly described in the model, though it is involved in the full calculation of CRi values and in other features of the model that have not been made available to you (such as nutrient uptake parameters).

In a more comprehensive description of predation, prey preference can be related to other aspects of the physiological state of the prey. For example, some prey not only deteriorate in their quality as food items, they actually become noxious or even toxic. It will be apparent from a combination of these interactions that there is scope for the development of a bloom of phytoplankton that, because of its poor nutritional value, fails to support a growth of an effective predator population.

What you should have noted

This section gives an overview of the primary learning points and other features that should have been uncovered following each experiment. For Experiments 6 and 7, there will be various other interactions beyond those described here.

Experiment 1

- Using a high **VED** will speed up the diffusion; it is best to use a low value in your first tests.
- Using a deep **MLD** provides more space (depth) for events; coupled with **VED**, this affects the rate at which nutrient (N) disperses.
- The peak N from the input will disperse, diffuse, very rapidly with a decrease in the concentration at the input depth, and an increase in concentrations either side (above and below – note the x-axis is depth !)
- If the concentration of '**N below MLD**' is high, then N will spread from the greatest depth, increasing concentrations throughout the water column.
- If, after the start, you decrease '**N input**' to zero, then the N in the system will gradually disappear (note the lower graph in the display. What is happening is that the N in the mixed layer is diffusing across the ergocline.

Experiment 2

- The core of the model is developed from that used for Experiment 1; you should appreciate the commentaries above for Experiment 1.
- Using a high **VED** will speed up the diffusion; it is best to use a low value in your first tests.
- Using a deep **MLD** provides more space (depth) for events; coupled with **VED**, this affects the rate at which the particles disperse.
- The peak particle suspension will disperse, rapidly. If 'Ascent rate' is zero, that dispersal will be even, trapped by the surface.
- If 'Ascent rate' is not zero, and noting that you can move the slider during the simulation, the particles will migrate up (to the left on the x-axis '**MLD depth**') or down (to the right on the x-axis '**MLD depth**').
- There is a loss of particles from the mixed layer; they diffuse out of the system at the greatest depth; you can slow that loss by setting a high positive 'Ascent rate' or speed it up by setting a negative 'Ascent rate'. You can see the results in the time plot (lower graph).
- The greater the **MLD**, the slower is the loss of particles.

Experiment 3

- The core of the model is developed from that used for Experiment 2; you should appreciate the commentaries above for Experiment 2, as well as for Experiments 1.
- The core of the model is similar to that for Experiment 2; you should observe the same test results for the particles, and understand the commentaries above for Experiments 1 and 2.
- The light level decreases exponentially with depth; it also decreases especially rapidly where the peak particle concentration is. The best way to see this is to set **VED** low, **MLD** deep, 'Ascent rate' as maximum, **ChlC** as maximum, run the simulation and move the '**Ascent rate**' slider up and down to observe the biomass migrating and its affects on the light level. If you move the

biomass deeper, it also disappears more rapidly as it is mixed out of the mixed layer (check the biomass vs time graph).

- If you repeat this again, but altering **ChlC**, you will observe the effect of changing the biomass pigmentation.

Experiment 4

- The core of the model is developed from that used for Experiment 3; you should appreciate the commentaries above for Experiment 3 as well as for the previous Experiments.
- Changing the geolocation and the season (i.e., the month), provides different light-dark patterns of light over each day. Thus the simulation now shows light and dark. Note that the light received at depth, and also the average light (avgE plot in the Light vs Time graph) changes markedly with where you move the peak biomass (changed using '**Ascent rate**').
- Altering **ChlC** has a marked effect on the value of avgE.
- When you use a high **VED**, and especially with a negative '**Ascent rate**', the value of avgE recovers rapidly as the pigmented biomass level declines (noting that there is no growth here).

Experiment 5

- The core of the model is developed from that used for Experiment 4; you should appreciate the commentaries above for Experiment 4 as well as for the previous Experiments.
- The growth of the biomass is controlled only by the amount of light. As the biomass grows, and especially with a high **ChlC**, so the growth rate decreases – check the appearance of the Biomass vs Time graph and also the Light vs Time graph.
- If you manipulate the **VED** rate, and the '**Ascent rate**', you can achieve a balanced population size, as plotted in the Biomass vs Time graph. You will need different values of **MLD** and the geolocation and seasonal light to achieve this. What is happening is that you are balancing off the growth (which becomes increasingly light-limited as the biomass grows throughout the water column) with the loss of biomass into deep waters at the ergocline (which is affected by the **VED** rate).

Experiment 6

- While the model used here is different those used in Experiments 1-5, it is important that you appreciate the commentaries for those experiments.
- Because of the complexity of the model, and the number of permutations, the following can provide only a general commentary.
- It is best to first explore this model with only 1 phytoplankton in the system. You could configure the phytoplankton differently, but then set either **initPhy[1]** or **initPhy[2]** as zero. Set the abiotic systems as you wish, and run the model. Then switch so that the other phytoplankton is set as zero, and see what happens.
- With only one phytoplankton present, a low **ChlCm** works well; this minimises self-shading from the population, and you can position them lower in the water column (note that a negative '**Ascent rate**' can also position the biomass near the ergocline resulting in a loss of biomass if the growth rate is low). In reality, phytoplankton will evolve to have a higher **ChlCm**, which may be good for the individual (which is the basis for evolutionary selection) but is not good for the

collective as it self-shades the whole system. When you introduce another phytoplankton (as a competitor) that interaction becomes more complex again.

- You may ask why would any phytoplankton not have a high **ChlCm**; the problem is that a high Chl:C in a situation with low biomass and high light is dangerous (there is a higher risk of photodamage), and it is also costly to maintain. Summer species evolve to need photoprotection to decrease the effects of high light (in the model, set **PinhK** high), but they may also migrate down to lower-lit waters as well, nearer the nutrients diffusing through the ergocline.
- Phototrophic organisms, such as phytoplankton, emerge from night time (during which they have been starved of C and will have increased their Chl:C towards the maximum set by **ChlCm** in the model) and so be equipped for high rates of photosynthesis. That rate of photosynthesis can be so high that the physiology cannot handle the incoming sugars, and they down-regulate photosynthesis. This causes an event termed the afternoon depression of photosynthesis. You can observe this event in the C-fixation vs Depth graph in the *Physiology window*; as light increases the C-fixation rate increases but then slumps even though there are sufficient light and nutrients. That slump occurs first in the surface waters (where there is more light) and only later, if at all, at lower depths.
- N-status and N:C vary with the amount of nutrient in the system (which later depends on the diffusion rate from the ergocline) and the rate of photosynthesis that brings in C. As the status declines with exhaustion of ammonium and then nitrate (see also the f-ratio plot in the *Physiology window*), so Chl:C also declines. This allows in more light into the water column as the total light attenuation decreases. In turn, excess light and a lack of nutrients creates more stress in the organisms so that not only does the growth rate decrease but death increases (so the [Growth-Death] value decreases even further).
- The '**Ascent rate**' value now sets the maximum rate of ascent when the phytoplankton are replete with N and lack C. As they exhaust the N nutrient (so N:C and N-status decline), they will migrate downwards. You can see the consequence of this in the Ascent rate vs Depth graph in the *Physiology window*. To begin with the cells migrate (assuming you have set **Ascent rate** >0) to the surface, but later they migrate down to where nutrient is diffusing in at the ergocline.
- Even with no ascent rate, a combination of light, nutrient and diffusion (of biomass and nutrients) rapidly shapes the vertical distribution of the biomass. If you experiment with a deep water system, and low nutrient levels, you will see the development of what is called a *deep chlorophyll maximum*.
- The position of the organisms in the water column will also be affected by combinations of the below-ergocline nutrient concentration, **VED**, geolocation and seasonal light and with cloud. Collectively these affect light and nutrient availability, which affects the rate of growth.
- Results from the *Sampling window* demonstrate the challenges for scientists in deciding at what depth to take samples. Often samples are taken at a fixed depth, either from the surface, or a few metres down at a location on the ships' hull. Taking samples at a range of depths requires the ship to halt; a series of samples can then be taken from different depths. Even so, experiments may be conducted on only a few of those sample depth; from the changing physiologies in the *Physiology window* you will see that trying to ascertain things like the C-fixation or growth rate for the biomass is a real problem; the physiologies change with depth and with the time of day at different depths.

Experiment 7

- The core of the model is developed from that used for Experiment 6; you should appreciate the commentaries above for Experiment 6 as well as for the previous Experiments.
- The big advance over Experiment 6 is that here you can explore the consequences of predation. Predation has several important roles in structuring the ecosystem and controlling the production of the phytoplankton. The factors that limit phytoplankton growth, light and nutrients, are countered as a consequence of predatory activity. Note that as the zooplankton population develops, the light penetrates deeper into the water column. The grazing activity also releases nutrients, in this instance as ammonium; note the changing value of the f-ratio as the zooplankton population grows. Note also that despite this evidence, the concentration of ammonium remains low until the phytoplankton biomass has been consumed. The reason for this is that ammonium is taken up by preference to the nitrate which is slowly entering the mixed layer at the pycnocline. In consequence, as soon as the ammonium is released by the zooplankton, it is consumed by the phytoplankton.
- The zooplankton migrates within the water column to balance satiation (obtaining sufficient food) against avoidance of the high light at the surface. Metazoan zooplankton, such as copepods, may migrate as much as 100s m each night, to feed near the surface in darkness, and then move into the dark (and cold) waters during the daylight hours.
- Prey preference (set by **CRi**) has a big impact on the results of the simulation. It does not matter how well configured are the phytoplankton, preference for grazing by the zooplankton will in due course result in that phytoplankton being grazed down. Species that may otherwise appear poorly configured may thus come to dominate; their slow growth is compensated for by slow loss rates.
- Altering the relative initial biomass levels of the phytoplankton and zooplankton alters the likelihood of match versus mismatch of prey or predator. With care, combinations of conditions can be located that provide for the development of something approaching a **steady-state**, rather than the strong oscillations in prey and predator that are more commonly seen.
- The relationship between predator and prey may also be affected by the development of nutrient stress that affects the dietary value of the prey. In the model this results in a lowered growth rate of the zooplankton, but in reality it could result in total rejection of that prey item.
- Cannibalism alters the dynamics of the interactions, but here that change is not so great as it could be with a metazoan zooplankton. For them, cannibalism often equates to eating the juvenile stages which has its greatest implications some way into the future. An absence of cannibalism could result in the sudden death, through starvation, of the whole zooplankton population; it is better that some survive at the cost of others.
- Results from the *Sampling window* demonstrate the challenges for scientists in deciding at what depth to take samples. The situation here is more complex again than in Experiment 6 because of the presence of the migrating zooplankton. Often samples are taken at a fixed depth, either from the surface, or a few metres down at a location on the ships' hull. Taking samples at a range of depths requires the ship to halt; a series of samples can then be taken from different depths. Even so, experiments may be conducted on only a few of those sample depth; from the changing physiologies in the *Physiology window* you will see that trying to ascertain things like the C-fixation, grazing rate by the zooplankton, or growth rate for the biomass is a real problem; the physiologies change with depth and with the time of day at different depths.
- You may wish to consider what would happen if one of the phytoplankton was configured as a mixoplankton, or if the zooplankton was reconfigured as a mixoplankton. This would result in a radical restructuring of the ecology. Mixoplankton are far more efficient as predators than are zooplankton; nutrients that would otherwise be released are internally recycled to boost

photosynthesis and thence growth. Mixoplankton are also far less likely to become nutrient-stressed as they can consume other organisms (including perhaps their competitors or predators) for nutrients. Mixoplankton are also typically highly motile, so they can best position themselves in the water column.

Some further thoughts and comments

Trait trade-offs and evolution

A 'trait' may be seen as a characteristic, but in science the former refers to a specific feature subject to evolutionary selection, while a characteristic is a more loose term.

You may at this point be wondering why nature cannot design the perfect organism with optimised traits across all of its specification, why selection does not provide the maximum growth rate, highest Chl:C, fastest migration (ascent) rates, best photoacclimation, least palatable etc. Of course, in a model you can do exactly that, but why then does nature not do this?

A particular topic of investigation in biology and ecology explores the concept of **trait trade-offs**. The idea is that every thing comes at a cost in materials and/or energy, and during its evolution an organism trades off these costs against the gains. The concept has parallels in aspects of economic theory.

Much has been written on this topic, but there are also many problems in trying to determine those costs and benefits. As an example of the challenges, consider the cost for a phytoplankton of using nitrate rather than ammonium. That cost equates to approaching 30% of the concurrent rate of photosynthesis. Surely, then, we must expect to see that growth on ammonium would be much faster than when using nitrate. The results from experiments, however, point to only a few percentage difference, if any. If such a massive cost difference (30%) does not result in an obvious difference in growth rates, why should the costs of traits accounting for only a few percentage of total organism expenditure result in a trait trade-off?

In reality, one trade off may be controlling the evolution of the maximum growth rate potential. It is notable that organisms living in conditions where there are plenty of resources have high growth rates, while those that have evolved to compete in oligotrophic ecosystems with low resource abundance can only grow slowly. Even if they are supplied with optimal conditions, those organisms from oligotrophic ecosystems still cannot grow quickly. The implication is that there is a cost in being able to grow quickly, and if the organism cannot attain that growth rate (for example because it is routinely starved) then it becomes stressed and dies. Organisms thus evolve a maximum growth rate potential that is aligned with the capacity of their environment to support that growth rate.

There is also a feature of evolution that is often overlooked that is of relevance in this discussion. While the emphasis in evolution is typically placed upon the optimisation of traits through evolution, there is also a process called **relaxed evolution**. First, recall that evolution occurs through the fixation of advantageous mutations. Mutations are random changes, most of which are deleterious, if not lethal. Useful mutations are very rare, so to acquire a perfect set of traits would represent an extreme event. Far more likely is that critical traits, that confer the most important advance for an organism in that time and place, are protected and are subjected to selection. The genes coding for other traits, of lesser importance, may be subjected to mutations that are deleterious but not critically so. This can over time result in the deterioration of trait expression and even in the loss of traits. This is the process of *relaxed evolution*.

In simple terms, an organism can only optimise a few and perhaps only a very few traits at a time. Relaxed evolution results in the deterioration of the others. This, then, represents the trait trade-off, not a specific cost trade-off in trait implementation.

There is another problem that will have become apparent from running Experiments 6 and 7 - conditions are constantly changing, so what traits is evolution targeting for optimisation? In laboratory conditions, the same exact conditions could be maintained for perhaps 100s or 1000s of generations. In nature,

conditions are changing sometimes literally by the minute. The diversity of life forms in plankton is vast. It may seem like the ocean represent a continuum of environmental conditions, but for the mainly microscopic life forms that inhabit these waters the environment is anything but the same. This variation, like that in a tropical rain forest, provides scope for evolution of many different permutations of trait expression.

A feature not considered thus far is the role of viruses. Viruses act upon plankton rather like a very specific predator. The spread and likelihood of viral attack is a function of the numeric abundance of the host organism. The most successful species is most likely to be affected by virus attack. Ultimately, then, success of an organism may rest in not being so overwhelmingly successful. A cryptic organism may be, over extreme time spans (>10000s years), very successful.

Climate change revisited

Climate change is altering the environmental conditions in which plankton grow and interact with each other. In the context of the conditions that you can vary in the experiments described here, the mixed layer depth (MLD) and vertical eddy diffusion rate (VED), and also the level of cloudiness, are changing over time and space scales. The MLD and VED affect the rates of nutrient exchange into the surface layer that supports primary production. Not considered here, the temperature and even the amount of CO₂ in the water that affects photosynthesis are also changing, as is the pH of the seawater, via a process called *ocean acidification*. Other human actions are affecting the flow of nutrients into coastal waters. As you will have seen, the interactions between nutrient loading and plankton growth are complex, affecting the growth of those organisms that directly need those nutrients, constrained by self-shading and linked to the physics, geolocation and seasonality of light, and also those organisms that depend on the primary production.

You will have noted that palatability of the phytoplankton is critically important. There are two facets to this. One relates to the type of plankton, to the species. This is related directly to biodiversity, a feature of ecosystems that is placed under increasing strain under climate change. The loss of a particular species from the water column at a time and space where it represents a key feed organism for animals can lead to the collapse of the food web. That is all the more likely if alternative species, perhaps of a similar organism type, is also absent.

The other facet relates to the nutritional status of the prey. The appropriate prey may be present, but its value as a food item may be poor, typically related to a lack of nutrient, either N or P. At the least, such a diet is processed less well, but at the worst nutrient stress can lead to the organism becoming noxious or even toxic. Such events can also lead to a positive feedback reaction where, because the prey are not eaten and nutrients not recycled, they become even more noxious. This can result in what is termed an **ecosystem disruptive algal bloom** (EDAB), which is a type (usually non-toxic) of **Harmful Algal Bloom** (HAB).

Emphasis here has been placed upon a simple phytoplankton-zooplankton system. This itself represents a gross simplification of reality. We now know that many important 'phytoplankton' and ca. 30% of the protist (single-celled) zooplankton are actually **mixoplankton**. These organisms photosynthesise and eat. Most phytoplankton (the protist phytoplankton) actually evolved from mixoplankton through the loss (by relaxed evolution) of an ability to feed; cyanobacteria, which are a type of phytoplankton, evolved first. The behaviours of mixoplankton are diverse and fascinating; this is a new paradigm in marine research. Mixoplankton include organisms that are of great importance for food-web dynamics, while other mixoplankton are EDAB or HAB species.

The zooplankton in Experiment 7 are considered as protists, with no complex life cycle. These are representative of most zooplankton in the ocean, but the zooplankton that directly support fisheries are metazoan. Metazoan zooplankton have complex multi-stage life cycles. As for all animals, the juvenile stages are especially sensitive to environmental conditions and also to the quality of their diet. Mismatch of prey with the predator is especially important for metazoan zooplankton; if good quality food is unavailable then few juveniles survive, creating a problem that persists over subsequent years as the effect of a poor production of eggs carries over.

The role of simulation models in climate change plankton research

To explore all of the complexity noted above presents an extreme challenge. It is a challenge that requires attention because of the role of plankton in biogeochemistry and in fisheries. This role is recognised in the Plankton Manifesto presented to the United Nations. The Manifesto can be accessed here:

<https://unglobalcompact.org/library/6242>

Describing the physical environment for the plankton is itself complex, while the plankton communities remain for the most part poorly studied as a holistic entity. Most attention has been paid to the larger metazoan zooplankton (copepods, krills) with little known about the gelatinous zooplankton, and far less in spatial and temporal scales about the microbial plankton. Much of the challenge relates to the vastness of the ocean set against the microscopic nature of the organisms and their interactions.

The only way we can pull all of the details together is to attempt to build and deploy simulation models. Those models need to reflect reality in their construction and behaviour. Specifically, we need models that can represent the biodiversity of the plankton. Traditionally that has not been so. Many models continue to place all phytoplankton and mixoplankton in one or very few groups; likewise zooplankton are often all placed in 1 or 2 groups. This would be akin to simulating life in terrestrial systems by placing all plants (moss, grass, shrubs, different trees etc.) in one group, and all animals (worms, insects, herbivorous and carnivorous mammals, birds etc.) in another group.

The plankton model used in Experiment 7 is in many ways more complex, more representative of reality, than plankton models using in climate change research. Hopefully, some of the readers of this document will rise to the challenge of enhancing the descriptions and thence of our understanding of the plankton.